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¹OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

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1 Introduction

This is part 2 of Deliverable 3.4.5, containing the proceedings of the final JEM workshop. This final meeting of the JEM Thematic Network is organized as a workshop during the Eight International Conference on Web-based Learning, ICWL 2009. This collocation aims to bring attention of the more general Web-based learning community to the issues involved in bringing mathematics teaching online.

This workshop aims to present to the wider audience the work and results of the partners of the Joining Educational Mathematics thematic network that has come to its conclusion after 3 years of activity. Partners of JEM are encouraged to present an overview of their work, with a special emphasis on how they have profited from cooperation within the network. The workshop is intended for a general audience interested in knowing what are the technologies and the methodologies that enhance teaching and learning of mathematics on the web.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to:

- lessons learned in teaching mathematics online
- case studies of eLearning in mathematics
- best practices for educational use of ICT in mathematics
- technological foundation for new eLearning applications
- semantic technologies for eLearning
- management of eLearning content
- work-in-progress, software demos

2 A. Heck, Harm Houwing, John Val, Georgia Papageorgiou and Lilia Ekimova Design and Implementation of an e-class About Continuous Dynamical Systems

In 2008, a small team of university and secondary school teachers in the Netherlands jointly developed an e-class for students in their final pre-university year (age: 17-18 yrs) about continuous dynamical systems. The e-class is an innovative way of teaching and learning mathematics and science by way of web-supported instruction in a blended learning approach. The e-learning ingredients are: an on-line instructional text, Java applets for students' explorative work, Java exercise applets, video clips of worked-out examples, and descriptions plus (computer) worksheets of real experiments. We present the design of the e-class plus some of the ICT ingredients of the e-class and their potential for teaching and learning dynamical systems in terms of principled design approaches to multimedia learning and pedagogical arrangements.

Design and Implementation of an e-Class About Continuous Dynamical Systems

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Abstract. In 2008, a small team of university and secondary school teachers in the Netherlands jointly developed an e-class for students in their final pre-university year (age: 17-18 yrs) about continuous dynamical systems. The e-class is an innovative way of teaching and learning mathematics and science by way of web-supported instruction in a blended learning approach. The e-learning ingredients are: an on-line instructional text, Java applets for students' explorative work, Java exercise applets, video clips of worked-out examples, and descriptions plus (computer) worksheets of real experiments. We present the design of the e-class plus some of the ICT ingredients of the e-class and their potential for teaching and learning dynamical systems in terms of principled design approaches to multimedia learning and pedagogical arrangements.

1 Background

The design and implementation of an e-class about continuous dynamical systems and the future plans regarding this form of blended teaching and learning cannot be seen apart from curriculum reforms and changes in the Dutch education system that took place in secondary education in the Netherlands in the last two decades, and from the reforms still under way (For details about the Dutch education system we refer to documents of the Ministry of Education, www.minocw.nl). In particular, the implementation in 1998 of the so-called 'Second Stage', i.e., the upper secondary education, had a strong influence because it introduced many new concepts for education and new national curricula. From 1998 on, students were only allowed to choose one of the fixed subject combinations, called 'profiles'. For our discussion of an e-class about continuous dynamical systems only the Nature profiles, that is, Nature & Technology and Nature & Health are relevant. The reason is that only students from these streams may select the newly introduced optional 'Mathematics D' subject and the 'Nature, Life, and Technology' subject (henceforth abbreviated as NLT), for which the course on continuous dynamical systems has been developed. In this paper we concentrate mostly on the intended use of the e-class in 'Mathematics D', because the focus on deep mathematics is strongest in this subject. Participants of the e-class in NLT do more practical work.

Not only the education system and the list of curriculum subjects changed in the last decades, but also the educational goals, subject matter, teaching materials, and teaching methods underwent significant changes. This holds especially

in mathematics and science education. The optional subject ‘Mathematics D’ aims at deepening and extending students’ mathematical knowledge and skills through separate modules. Statistics and probability theory, dynamical systems, or a topic like complex numbers are examples of extensions. The deepening happens the students’ engagement in topics taken from a scientific or technical context such as cryptography, graph theory and discrete mathematics, or in integrated science topics, which aim to create coherence between the different subjects of the sciences and to make the natural sciences and technology more attractive. The list of possible contents of ‘Mathematics D’ illustrates that this optional subject aims to tackle the problems that

- exact sciences have little attraction for students because the relevant school subjects are not challenging and seem disconnected with new developments in society, mathematics, science and technology;
- too few students choose a follow-up study or profession in these fields, as a consequence of this lack of appeal.

The implementation of the new curricula and ‘Mathematics D’ have to contend with difficulties like a rather short preparatory period and a shortage of qualified teachers with enough scientific baggage for teaching and developing the new mathematics and science subjects. To tackle these problems and to bridge the gap between secondary school and higher education at all levels, a network was started in 2007 in the region of Amsterdam, called the ‘its academy’ (www.itsacademy.nl). Within this network, staff members from about forty secondary schools and four higher education institutes jointly design and implement the new offer of curriculum materials. Because of the real danger that not enough students would choose ‘Mathematics D’ or NLT, and consequently teaching can only be done cost-effectively within a cluster of schools, the potential of e-learning in conjunction with classroom activities at cluster level and practical work in the ‘its-labs’ at the higher education institutes has been examined. In 2007, a pilot study of e-classes for ‘Mathematics D’ with a study load of 40 study hours was carried out on the topic of discrete dynamical systems. We refer to [9] for a report about the experiences with one of the e-classes from the pilot project. For the purpose of this paper it suffices to mention that it was overall a great success. Most of the students appreciated that an e-class offered them the opportunity to work with and learn from screen casts, to consult their peers and the teacher in the chat room, to plan more or less their working hours, to build executable computer models, and to learn a lot in a mixed and attractive approach.

Guided by what had been learned in the pilot study and during the use of the materials in school practice in 2008, a team of two secondary school teachers in mathematics, two international master students in the Master of Mathematics & Science Education [16] at the University of Amsterdam with mathematics as their discipline specialty, and a university researcher and developer in mathematics and mathematics education set out to develop an e-class about the mathematical approach to processes of change, and in particular to continuous dynamical models. These are models of systems that can move continuously from

one state into another. In the e-class the main focus is on models in the form of a differential equation

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x, t), \quad x(t_0) = x_0,$$

where x stands in the model for the state of system that can be expressed as a quantity (temperature, position, concentration, etc.), which changes with time t . Lessons include not only methods for solving a differential equation in an exact or approximate manner, but also give students the opportunity to analyze systems without actually solving them and to get acquainted with modern applications of the theory.

In this paper we discuss the design and implementation of the e-class, and we elaborate on the following ICT ingredients of the web-supported blended learning approach:

- The integral on-line text explaining the basics of ordinary differential equations and aiming at an increase of students' understanding about how professionals such as mathematical biologists, physicists, and applied mathematicians use dynamical systems to investigate real phenomena;
- The Java applets for students' explorative work (for example, for plotting of line element fields, solution curves, phase portraits, etc.);
- The Java exercise applets in which students can solve randomized exercises online in a step-by-step approach while the environment checks correctness of steps made;
- The video clips that help students in their learning of mathematics by provision of worked-out examples and sample exercises;
- The video clips (screen casts) with instructions for learning to work with accompanying software such as the modeling tool of Coach and the Java applets for exploration or practicing;
- The descriptions and (computer) worksheets of real experiments that students can do at home or at school and that introduce them to applications and model building. The real experiments spice up the lessons and relate the to-be-learned mathematics with real world phenomena such as the change in time of the head of a beer, the outflow of water from a bottle, biking and sprinting, and so on.

2 What Does the e-Class Look Like?

We discuss in this section the mathematical contents of the course, the instructional set-up, and some of the ICT aspects and design choices concerning the e-class.

2.1 Mathematical Content of the e-Class

Students who participate in the e-class are expected to be mature from mathematical point of view, in the sense that it is assumed that they already have

knowledge and skills about derivatives and antiderivatives. This makes the mathematical content of the e-class viable for students in their final school year. The content consists of the following parts:

1. Homogeneous linear first-order differential equations in one dimension;
2. Homogeneous nonlinear first-order differential equations in one dimension;
3. Nonhomogeneous linear first-order differential equations in one dimension;
4. Nonhomogeneous linear high-order differential equations in one dimension;
5. Autonomous linear first-order differential equations in two dimensions;
6. Autonomous nonlinear first-order differential equations in two dimensions;
7. Chaotic systems.

However, it must also be noted that the content and set-up of the e-class is flexible and may consist of a selection of the above elements. Students participating in an NLT e-class will only do the basic parts 1-3. They may focus less on the mathematical theory, but instead do more practical work and applications. For example, these students can study parts 4 and 7 through computer experiments. In this set-up the minimum study load is 40 hours; Students who participate in a ‘Mathematics D’ e-class may extend the minimum programme (parts 1-4, 7), which has a study load of 40 hours, with a further study of autonomous 2-dimensional systems (parts 5 and 6, also with a study load of 40 hours). However, this is only possible if students are familiar with complex numbers and/or basics of linear algebra. This brings an extra study load of 40 hours, for which there is also space in the examination programme. This way, the study load of the e-class on continuous dynamical systems can range from 40 to 120 hours. A study guide for teachers explains the options, proposes a time schedule, and gives suggestions for assessment.

2.2 Web-Supported Instruction in a Blended Learning Approach

One of the ideas behind the set-up of an e-class was to develop a rich electronic learning environment equipped with study guides, digitized lesson materials, software for learning and doing mathematics and science, video instructions, animations, (self-)assessments, communication tools for students and teachers to chat and discuss, and so on. The blended approach, here considered as a combination of online learning and face-to-face education at school, is central. Various methods of delivery of instruction are used in such way that schools, where there are only few students who choose ‘Mathematics D’ or NLT, are still able to offer the course effectively by participation in a cluster of schools. Actually, the broader definition of [11] for blended learning in higher education — “learning that is facilitated by the effective combination of different modes of delivery, models of teaching and styles of learning, and founded on transparent communication amongst all parties involved with a course.” — seems to us applicable to the e-class setting for secondary schools. We will adopt this definition, acknowledging that there is no universally accepted definition of blended learning [2, 23] and that there are some serious doubts about its conceptual integrity [19].

In the rest of this article we look into the different modes of delivery, models of teaching, and styles of learning.

The set-up of the e-class is both simple and complex. All course materials are available online in a Sakai-based virtual learning environment (henceforth abbreviated as VLE). There is one master copy of the e-class, from which clones are constructed for use by real classes. The teacher of a cloned class can adapt the lesson materials to the ability level of his or her students, or give it a more personal touch. The choice for Sakai [21] was based on the fact that almost full responsibility for the e-class can be transferred to the individual teacher who can, for example, make his/her own assignments, invite students and colleague teachers, and so on. Instructions for students regarding the mathematical software for dealing with differential equation and for giving explanations of sample exercises are preferably given by means of screen casts created and made available in the VLE. A screen cast is a digital movie in which the setting is partly or wholly a computer screen and in which audio narration describes or explains the story on the on-screen action. This way, students do not need separate instructions on tool use or long manuals on how to use each tool. Students are requested to hand in their answers to some of the online assignments through the request-and-delivery system for exercises inside the VLE: this homework could be a Word document, an Excel sheet, a result file of a computer simulation made with the modeling tool of Coach [10], or whatever appropriate digital document. For personal transfer of documents between a student and the teacher (for example, to get dedicated help or advice on a task, or for the simple reasons that homework could not be delivered within the scheduled time frame), the drop box facility of the VLE is convenient. Students can use the chat tool in the e-class to keep in touch with their peers and the teacher during the course: they can discuss exercises, ask each other for further information or explanation, and so on. And last but not least, students are still expected to meet the teacher and their peers at school and ask questions, discuss homework, collaborate, and so forth. After all, face-to-face contact in education remains highly valued! The assessment of students' work is expected to be in accordance with the way they have studied the subject content, i.e., through written tests, practical work, partial credit for homework, etc.

The complexity of the e-class setting lies in the well-known fact that mere use of ICT in education does not lead to good quality of learning. The major challenge for a long time has been how to find the right blended learning arrangement with regard to content, knowledge construction, and communication within a regular curriculum setting [12, 14, 15] that leads to meaningful learning, and how to initiate, sustain, and structure interaction and enhance its quality [5]. In the design of the e-class we have based our decisions mainly on the teachers' experiences, research-based design principles of multimedia learning (for a collection of papers see [18]), and principles of learning sciences for the design of pedagogical arrangements (for a collection of papers see [22]).

Fig. 1 is a screenshot showing the content menu bar to the relevant parts of the mathematics course, which is always at the students' disposal, and a fragment

of the lesson text. This fragment illustrates that the online instructional material is intended to be highly interactive. In this particular case, an applet, created with the ‘Easy Java Simulations’ (EJS) software tool [3], offers the opportunity to draw line element field of differential equations and plot solution curves (by clicking in the drawing canvas). A student can first predict a particular solution in the format of a mathematical formula and then can compare the plot of his or her prediction with a computed solution curve.

The last line in the screen shot in Fig. 1 illustrates the mathematical formatting in MathML. This has been realized by using ASCIIMathML [1]. Some webbrowsers need MathPlayer for the display of the mathematical formulas and users of the e-class are informed about these mild system requirements.

Fig. 1. Screenshot of a lesson fragment in the e-class illustrating the use of an EJS applet.

Another illustrative example of user interactivity is shown in Fig. 2, in which GeoGebra [4] is used to create a graphical representation of an adjustable complex number. The hope and expectation is that students get a better understanding of the geometrical meaning of complex numbers by exploration with such applets. The screenshot also illustrates the authors’ intention to make the layout of the instructional material similar to a classical textbook: for example, frames with colored backgrounds are used to summarize or highlight the essentials.

For online learning and practicing algebra and calculus, the e-class makes use of exercise applets, developed in collaboration with researchers and developers at

Fig. 2. Screenshot of a lesson fragment in the e-class illustrating the use of a GeoGebra applet.

the Freudenthal Institute in the Netherlands. The reader is referred to [7] for a detailed discussion of the design and use of such applets. Here it suffices to show some screenshots. Fig. 3 illustrates how students can do some calculation step by step on the computer; in this particular case it is a rehearsal of the substitution technique in computing an integral. In each step the student's answer is validated so that the student knows whether (s)he is still on the right track.

Fig. 3. Screenshot of an exercise applet about integration.

2.3 Use of Executable Computer Models

The focus of the e-class about continuous dynamical systems is not solely on analytical solution methods. Students should realize that the most interesting mathematical models of real phenomena that can be expressed in the form of differential equations can only be solved numerically. Easy Java Simulations [3] software has been used in illustrative examples in the lesson text, but when students have to create computer models from scratch they are expected to use the modeling tool of Coach [10]. Fig. 6, taken from [8], shows a graphical model representing the Keller model of sprinting [13], which is the following initial value problem for the speed of the sprinter:

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = F - \frac{v}{\tau}, \quad v(0) = 0.$$

Here v is the sprinter's speed represented by a rectangular icon, and F and τ are constants. The acceleration a in the graphical model is represented by an inflow that depends on v , F , and τ . Our experience is that high school students can work well with such system dynamics based modeling tool, certainly when they can make the link between the graphical representation and the mathematical notation of differential equations. They also enjoy doing this.

Fig. 6. Screenshot of a graphical model and simulation of a sprint.

2.4 Screen Casting in the e-Class

The chatroom in the VLE is a communication channel in the e-class in which students help and motivate each other. The main idea is that students working at home could overcome difficulties (for example, with the ICT tools or with the underlying mathematics) through discussions with their peers and the teacher in the chatroom.

Besides the chat facility, screen casting is the killer application, appreciated by all students. The aim of screen casting is to allow students to:

- see and hear the thinking and explanation of a teacher when doing a task;
- watch whenever and as many times they want;

- go stepwise through an instruction;
- look at the whole process and not only at the final result of an activity.

The main benefits of the screen casts in the e-class are that they support student learning outside the classroom, function in case of software instruction better than user manuals or support pages, and help the teacher in the sense that (s)he can make optimal use of the face-to-face contact time with students. The success of this form of screen casting can be underpinned by research-based principles of multimedia learning. We refer the interested reader to [9].

2.5 Real Experiments in the e-Class

The e-class about dynamical systems also emphasizes doing real experiments regarding phenomena that can be mathematically modeled by differential equations. The experiments must be simple enough so that students can do them outside school. An example is the collapse of beer foam, which can be modeled by an exponential decay model. When also the liquid content of the glass is taken into account a linear system of differential equations comes into play. The interested reader is for a detailed description of the modeling of beer collapse referred to [6]. Here it suffices to mention that a video recording of the phenomenon with a webcam will do the job in combination with video analysis and modeling in the Coach environment. Fig. 7 shows a screenshot of a video analysis of the head of an alcohol-free beer in a cylindrical glass. Data collection took place by automated point tracking and an exponential regression curve is plotted with the measured data in the background.

Fig. 7. Screenshot of a video analysis of the head of an alcohol-free beer.

The exponential decay model of beer foam corresponds with the following ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{WetFoamH}(t) = -\frac{1}{\tau} \cdot \text{WetFoamH}(t),$$

where τ is the lifetime of the beer foam. The graphical representation in the modeling tool of Coach 6 is shown in Fig. 8. The decay model with the most suitable values of initial height and lifetime matches the measured data rather well, except for the first stage.

Fig. 8. Screenshot of the exponential decay model of beer foam height.

It goes without saying that many a student is enthusiastic about such applications of mathematics. We are of opinion that motivating and engaging students in mathematics activities, and having them think about the problem and try to test their ideas matter more than whether a model is perfectly correct from scientific point of view.

References

1. ASCIIMathML. <http://www1.chapman.edu/~jipsen/mathml/asciimath.html>
2. Bonk, C.J., Graham, C.R. (eds.): The handbook of blended learning: Global perspectives, local designs. San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer Publishing (2006).
3. Easy Java Simulations. www.um.es/fem/Ejs/ [15 Aug 2009].
4. GeoGebra. www.geogebra.org [15 Aug 2009].
5. Hannafin, M.J.: Interaction strategies and emerging instructional technologies: Psychological perspectives. *Canad. J. Educ. Commun.* 18(3), 167-179 (1989). [Online], Available: www.cjlt.ca/index.php/cjlt/article/view/274/208 [15 Aug 2009].
6. Heck, A.: Bringing Reality into the Classroom. Proceeding of the 9th International Conference on Technology ion mathematics Teaching (ICTMT9), Metz, France, 2009 (to appear).
7. Heck, A., Boon, P., Bokhove, C., Koolstra, G.: Applets for learning school algebra and calculus. *Electronic Proceedings e+Calculus, 1st JEM Workshop* (2007). [Online], Available: www.jem-thematic.net/node/158
8. Heck, A., Ellermeijer, A.L.: Giving student the run of sprinting models. *Am. J. Phys.* (accepted for publication).
9. Heck, A., Houwing, H., de Beurs, C.: An e-Class in action: Experiences with ICT-intensive teaching and learning of discrete dynamical models at secondary school.

- Electron. J. of e-Learn. 7(1), 41-52 (2009). [Online], Available: www.ejel.org [15 Aug 2009]
10. Heck, A., Kedzierska, E., Ellermeijer, T.: Design and implementation of an integrated computer working environment. *J. Comput. Math. Sci. Teach.* 28(2), 147-161 (2009)
 11. Heinze, A., Procter, C.: Reflections on the use of blended learning. *Education in a changing environment - ECE Conference Proceedings*, University of Salford (2004) [Online], Available: www.ece.salford.ac.uk/proceedings/papers/ah_04.rtf [15 Aug 2009]
 12. John, P.D., Wheeler, S.: *The digital classroom: Harnessing technology for the future*. New York, NY: Routledge (2008).
 13. Keller, J.B.: Optimal velocity in a race. *Am. Math. Monthly.* 81(5), 474-480 (1974).
 14. Kerres, M., de Witt, C.: A didactical framework for the design of blended learning arrangements. *J. Educ. Media* 28(2/3) 101-113 (2003).
 15. Laurillard, D.: *Rethinking university teaching: A framework for the effective use of learning technologies* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge Falmer (2002).
 16. Master of mathematics and Science Education. University of Amsterdam. www.science.uva.nl/research/amstel/dws/masters/
 17. MathPlayer. Design Science. www.dessci.com/en/products/mathplayer/
 18. Mayer, R.E. (ed.): *The Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press (2005) .
 19. Oliver, M., Trigwell, K.: Can 'blended learning' be redeemed? *E-Learn.* 2(1), 17-26 (2005). [Online], Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2304/elea.2005.2.1.17> [15 Aug 2009]
 20. Paivio, A.: *Mental representations: A dual coding approach*. Oxford: Oxford University Press (1986).
 21. Sakai. <http://sakaiproject.org/portal>
 22. Sawyer, R.K. (ed.): *The Cambridge handbook of the learning sciences*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press (2006).
 23. Whitelock, D., Jelfs, A.: Editorial. *J. Educ. Media* 28(2/3), 99-100 (2003).

3 M. Antonia Huertas

E-learning of mathematics at the UOC in the JEM context

An overview of the teaching, innovation and research that people of the UOC have been doing during the JEM project period, with a special emphasis on how we have profited from participation and cooperation within the network. The main subject of the work presented is e-learning of mathematics for distance high education: methodologies, technologies and best practices developed in the JEM network project context.

- Mathematical E-learning Project (MEL): an study of the MEL best practices at the Spanish Universities
- Digital locution and automatic verbalization of formulae
- Open repositories for mathematical resources
- Mathematics on the web representation and communication: standards and tools
- Mathematical software for e-learning and Interactive didactic material
- Automatic tutorials and assessment in web based education
- Multilingual challenges and opportunities of the e-learning scenario

E-learning of mathematics (MEL) at the UOC in the JEM context

M. Antonia Huertas

Final JEM Workshop
RWTH Aachen University, Aachen (Germany)
August 21, 2009

People involved

- César Córcoles
- Angel A. Juan
- Teresa Sancho
- Toni Pérez
- Mireia Pascual
- Julià Minguillon
- Enric Mor
- Lourdes Meler
- Roger Griset
- ...

The UOC

- Distance learning – Web based learning (14 years)
- Completely VLE
- 45,000+ students
- Typical student:
 - >25 y/o
 - Fully employed
 - Long forgotten math

Our advantage

We already “live” inside a computer lab, even if it’s a widely distributed one, so integration of ICT in the classroom is quite natural.

Mathematical e-learning at the UOC: the starting point three years ago

- ❑ Virtual classroom:
 - Communication forums
 - Mainly PDF, traditional non-interactive, content centred didactical material
 - Mathematical software used: Maple, Wiris.
 - Calendar, agenda, and temporalization guides
 - Continuous assessment model: students sending exercises via e-mail to the instructor

- ❑ Face-to-face final examinations
 - Paper based

Virtual classroom

> 75.004 Álgebra > Álgebra aula 1 - Cristina Steegmann Pascual

Álgebra aula 1

[Cristina Steegmann Pascual](#)

[Volver a vista de consultor](#)

Comunicación

Tablón general [1]

Tablón [23]

Foro [166]

Participantes del aula [4]

Planificación

Actividades

Calendario semestral

Plan docente

Recursos

Materiales y fuentes

Evaluación

Entrega de actividades

Notas eval. continua

Notas finales

Planificación

2009 febrero

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2009 marzo

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Fecha	Título	Cita
26	GE0	Guía de estudio

Fecha	Título	Cita
1	GE1	Guía de estudio
6	PEC1	Inicio
8	GE2	Guía de estudio
15	GE3	Guía de estudio
16	PEC1	Entrega
18	PEC1	Solución
20	PEC2	Inicio
22	GE4	Guía de estudio
24	PEC1	Calificación
29	GE5	Guía de estudio
30	PEC2	Entrega

Virtual classroom: communication

> 75.004 Álgebra > Álgebra aula 1 - Cristina Steegmann Pascual

Álgebra aula 1
Cristina Steegmann Pascual

[Volver a vista de consultor](#)

Comunicación

- Tablón general [1]
- Tablón [23]
- Foro [166]
- Participantes del aula [4]

Planificación

- Actividades
- Calendario semestral
- Plan docente

Recursos

- Materiales y fuentes

Evaluación

- Entrega de actividades
- Notas eval. continua
- Notas finales

Planificación

2009 febrero

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2009 marzo

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Fecha	Título	Cita
26	GE0	Guía de estudio

Fecha	Título	Cita
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6	PEC1	Inicio
8	GE2	Guía de estudio
15	GE3	Guía de estudio
16	PEC1	Entrega
18	PEC1	Solución
20	PEC2	Inicio
22	GE4	Guía de estudio
24	PEC1	Calificación
29	GE5	Guía de estudio
30	PEC2	Entrega

Virtual classroom: temporalization

> 75.004 Álgebra > Álgebra aula 1 - Cristina Steegmann Pascual

Álgebra aula 1
Cristina Steegmann Pascual

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Comunicación

- Tablón general [1]
- Tablón [23]
- Foro [166]
- Participantes del aula [4]

Planificación

- Actividades
- Calendario semestral
- Plan docente

Recursos

- Materiales y fuentes

Evaluación

- Entrega de actividades
- Notas eval. continua
- Notas finales

Planificación

2009 febrero

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9	10	11	12	13	14	15
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2009 marzo

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9	10	11	12	13	14	15
16	17	18	19	20	21	22
23	24	25	26	27	28	29
30	31					

Fecha	Título	Cita
26	GE0	Guía de estudio

Fecha	Título	Cita
1	GE1	Guía de estudio
6	PEC1	Inicio
8	GE2	Guía de estudio
15	GE3	Guía de estudio
16	PEC1	Entrega
18	PEC1	Solución
20	PEC2	Inicio
22	GE4	Guía de estudio
24	PEC1	Calificación
29	GE5	Guía de estudio
30	PEC2	Entrega

Virtual classroom: resources

> 75.004 Álgebra > Álgebra aula 1 - Cristina Steegmann Pascual

Álgebra aula 1 [Volver a vista de consultor](#)

[Cristina Steegmann Pascual](#)

Comunicación

- Tablón general [1]
- Tablón [23]
- Foro [166]
- Participantes del aula [4]

Planificación

- Actividades
- Calendario semestral
- Plan docente
- Recursos**
- Materiales y fuentes

Evaluación

- Entrega de actividades
- Notas eval. continua
- Notas finales

Planificación

2009 febrero

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Virtual classroom: resources

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- Notas eval. continua
- Notas finales

Materiales de la asignatura

- Álgebra pdf
- Módulo 1. Teoría de conjuntos pdf
- Módulo 2. Números naturales pdf
- Módulo 3. Elementos de álgebra lineal y geometría pdf
- Módulo 4. Sistemas de ecuaciones lineales pdf
- Módulo 5. Aplicaciones lineales pdf
- Módulo 6. Transformaciones geométricas pdf

Bibliografía recomendada

Fuentes de Información

- Enlaces de interés
- Bases de datos (Matemáticas)
- Enciclopedias y diccionarios (Matemáticas)
- Gartner

Virtual classroom

> 75.004 Álgebra > Álgebra aula 1 - Cristina Steegmann Pascual

Álgebra aula 1 [Volver a vista de consultor](#)

[Cristina Steegmann Pascual](#)

Comunicación

Tablón general [1]

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Planificación

Actividades

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29	GE5	Guía de estudio
30	PEC2	Entrega

Problems and opportunities in Mathematical E-Learning in distance edu

Problems

Students are always alone

- Didactical material and resources need to be complete, guides, interactive material...
- Mathematical notation: reading and writing maths in web add difficulty to learning.
- Improvement of assessment for the learning process

Opportunities

Students have always a PC

- Easy to use ICT and mathematical software in an integrated way
- Save time in the a virtual campus, not to have to move to the centre, etc.

Overview of the MEL projects developed at the UOC in the context of JEM

- Mathematical E-learning (MEL) at the Spanish Universities Project
- “Really web based materials” Project
- Mathematical notation on the web:
 - E-mail Formulas Project
 - Verbalization of formulas Project (with *Maths for More*)
 - Locutions of formulas Project (RODOLFO Project)
- Open repository for digital resources: E-math++ & PERSONAL(ONTO) ProjectS
- Automatic tutorials and assessment for Logic course: SELL Project

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Mathematical E-learning (MEL) at the Spanish Universities Project

What was the MEL situation in Spain (face-to-face and distance universities)?

- Mathematical Software
- VLE and Platforms
- Resources and methodologies
- Best practices
- EEES adaptation
- Etc.

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Mathematical E-learning (MEL) Project : Results examples

P1 – Uso actual de software matemático-estadístico x CC.AA.

P8 – Valoración uso software mat-est x CC.AA.

<http://cimanet.uoc.edu/mel>

P2 – Uso actual entornos online + Internet x CC.AA.

P9 – Valoración uso entornos online + Internet x CC.AA.

P3 – Integración TIC en procesos evaluación x CC.AA.

P4 – Uso material o recursos en Inglés x CC.AA.

“Really web based materials” Project

- Mathematics on the web representation and communication: standards and tools
- Browser support finally allows us to offer web based materials in XHTML+MathML format.
- LaTeX based authoring + TeX4ht +
- ...allow us to embed Wiris applets in order to have a symbolic calculator *in* the material
- We can teach mathematics, and forget about [some] algorithms and memorization

Result: web based interactive courses

[Introducció](#)
[Objectius](#)
[Coneixements previs](#)
Nombres complexos
[Forma binòmica](#)
[Representació. Pla complex](#)
[Operacions en forma binòmica](#)
[Forma polar](#)
[Operacions en forma polar](#)
[Equacions de circumferències](#)
Funcions complexes
[Funcions de variable complexa](#)
[Funcions polinòmiques](#)
[Funcions exponencials](#)
[Funcions trigonomètriques](#)
[Derivació i integració](#)
[Límits](#)
[Derivació](#)
[Integració. Primitives](#)
[Integral de línia](#)
[Mètodes d'integració](#)
[Transformada de Fourier](#)
[Transformada de Fourier](#)
[Resum](#)
[Resum](#)

1.5. Operacions amb nombres complexos en forma polar

Producte i divisió

Si considerem dos nombres complexos escrits en la forma trigonomètrica

$$z_1 = r_1(\cos \theta_1 + i \sin \theta_1)$$

$$z_2 = r_2(\cos \theta_2 + i \sin \theta_2)$$

i realitzem el seu producte, obtindrem:

$$z_1 \cdot z_2 = r_1 \cdot r_2 (\cos \theta_1 + i \sin \theta_1)(\cos \theta_2 + i \sin \theta_2) =$$

$$r_1 \cdot r_2 (\cos \theta_1 \cdot \cos \theta_2 - \sin \theta_1 \cdot \sin \theta_2 + i(\cos \theta_1 \cdot \sin \theta_2 + \sin \theta_1 \cdot \cos \theta_2))$$

Utilitzem les propietats trigonomètriques

$$\cos(\alpha + \beta) = \cos \alpha \cos \beta - \sin \alpha \sin \beta$$

$$\sin(\alpha + \beta) = \cos \alpha \sin \beta + \sin \alpha \cos \beta$$

Les propietats de la trigonometria asseguren que aquest resultat és

$$z_1 \cdot z_2 = r_1 \cdot r_2 (\cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2) + i \sin(\theta_1 + \theta_2)).$$

Per tant, es compleix la propietat següent:

Donats dos nombres complexos en forma polar

$$z_1 = (r_1)_{\theta_1} \quad i \quad z_2 = (r_2)_{\theta_2}$$

- **Producte.** El mòdul del producte és el producte de mòduls i l'argument del producte és la suma d'arguments:

An integrated symbolic calculator...

An integrated symbolic calculator...

En aquesta activitat podeu experimentar amb una funció complexa i visualitzar les imatges...

- d'un punt "blau", que podreu moure interactivament i la imatge es mostra com "vermell".
- d'un segment. Podreu recórrer el segment movent un punt de color magenta descriu i així es genera la imatge. També podeu canviar interactivament els extrems del segment.
- de la circumferència unitat, que podreu recórrer manualment movent un punt vermell.

Si voleu treballar amb la funció que ha generat la figura 11 del material en paper, és $f(z) = 2z - z^2$.

Presentació d'original i imatge en un mateix tauler

Edició | Operacions | Símbols | Anàlisi | Matrius | Unitats | Combin

UOC

Done

Per a visualitzar ràpidament la representació de les funcions superposats, amb la calculadora Wiris es pot fer servir un un altre per als de la imatge. [Vegeu exemples de com es fa la representació superposada o en dos taulers separats.](#)

La representació gràfica d'una funció complexa utilitza el domini i un altre per a la imatge; aquests dos plans es superposen (en aquest darrer cas, s'ha de diferenciar d'altre de la imatge; per exemple, amb diferents colors). Obs

Mathematical notation on the web: e-mail

- Mathematical communication by e-mail UOC editor is difficult
 - Attaching documents
 - Inventing auto coding
 - Explaining without writing formulas

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Mathematical notation on the web: e-mail

UOC BUZÓN Cerrar

Huevo

Enviar mensaje Adjuntar Guardar Contactos

A:

Copia a:

De: Àgata Lapedriza Garcia

Asunto:

Archivos adjuntos:

Formato enriquecido **Herramienta de fórmulas**

Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
 Estudis d'Informàtica, Multimedia i Telecomunicació.
 Rbla. del Poblenou, 156 08018 - Barcelona

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Enviar mensaje Adjuntar Guardar Contactos

A:

Copia a:

De: Àgata Lapedriza Garcia

Asunto:

Archivos adjuntos:

Hola,

nos piden estudiar la convergencia de

$$\int_1^2 \frac{x+3}{x^2-1} dx$$

Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
 Estudis d'Informàtica, Multimedia i Telecomunicació.
 Rbla. del Poblenou, 156 08018 - Barcelona

Previsualització:

Hola,

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Previsualització:

Hola,
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 $\int_1^2 \frac{x+3}{x^2-1} dx$

Mathematical notation on the web: verbalization

- Mathematical formulae:
 - Not a common language
 - Rigorous notation
- Online environment
 - It doesn't allow to hear teacher's explanations
 - It doesn't allow to see the writing of expressions in real time
 - Teachers don't know how students read or understand
- Student's profile
 - Adults with family and professional experience
 - Short time for studying
 - Insufficient or forgotten previous mathematical knowledge

Mathematical notation on the web: verbalization

- Develop a mathematical expression verbalization tool.
With WIRIS Formula Editor Verbalization tool
Maths for More
- Integrate this tool in the online study material.

Verbalization tool

How does it work?

1. Mouse over formula
2. Formula text appears
3. The formula is verbalized in real time!

La idea básica de cada uno de los tipos es la siguiente:

- Los números naturales son los que sirven para realizar recuentos, y se designan con la letra \mathbb{N} .
- Los números enteros permiten contar tanto lo que se tiene como lo que se debe, y se designan con el símbolo \mathbb{Z} .
- Los números racionales dan cuenta de las situaciones en la que se tienen objetos fragmentados, y se designan con el símbolo \mathbb{Q} .
- Los números denominados irracionales, entre los que se encuentran las raíces de los números primos, se designan con el símbolo \mathbb{R} .

Cada tipo de números descrito contiene al anterior:

$$\mathbb{N} \subseteq \mathbb{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{Q} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$$

Es decir, todo número natural también es un número entero, todo número entero es un número racional, y así sucesivamente. Su vez, real.

A la hora de reconocer la clase de un número, debe tenerse en cuenta que un número puede expresarse de varias formas. Por ejemplo, el número natural 3 puede expresarse, también como número racional, como es el caso de $\frac{3}{1}$.

actividad 1

Verbalization tool

Different verbalizations depending on the mathematical area

- Examples. d , $(')$: different uses and meanings

Las propiedades básicas de la derivada son:

- La derivada de una suma de funciones es la suma de $f'(x) + g'(x)$.
- La derivada de una función es igual a la constante multiplicada por la derivada de la función. Es $(k \cdot f(x))' = k \cdot f'(x)$.

Editor...

Dicho de otra manera, el determinante de una matriz A por la traspuesta de, entre paréntesis, A por la traspuesta de, entre paréntesis, la matriz de adjuntos de A .

Editor...

La inversa de A igual a 1 partido por el determinante de, entre paréntesis, A por la traspuesta de, entre paréntesis, la matriz de adjuntos de A .

Editor...

La integral de la suma de funciones es igual a la suma de la integral de las funciones.

$$\int (f(x) + g(x)) dx = \int f(x) dx + \int g(x) dx$$

La integral del producto de un número por una función es igual al producto del número por la integral de la función.

$$\int k \cdot f(x) dx = k \int f(x) dx$$

Por ejemplo:

La integral de k por f de x , diferencial de x igual a k por la integral de f de x diferencial de x .

Editor...

Verbalization tool

Work with the formula

- Click the Edit button
- Math Formula Editor
- Appears with the formula and its verbalization.

This is the
WIRIS Formula Editor

Este intervalo.

- un intervalo abierto por un extremo ejemplo, $[-2, 3)$ es un intervalo mientras que -2

Gráficamente, se puede representar el intervalo sea cerrado poniendo un punto en el/los extremo/s en los que el

Editor...

El intervalo, semiabierto por la derecha, de origen menos 2 y extremo 3

3 = $\frac{9}{3} = \sqrt{9}$

actividad 1 | actividad 2

Verbalization tool: technology

- Requirements
 - Mathematical formula
 - MathML
 - LaTeX (ASCII MathML converts LaTeX to MathML)
- Process
 - Tree representation of the formula
 - Mathematical common constructions
 - Semantic information
 - Mathematical area: Algebra & Calculus (math areas of the course)
 - Transcription
 - Transform the content of the tree's elements into text
 - Available in any language

Verbalization tool: improvements

- Generate audible output
 - Connect transcription system with synthesizer
- Enhance the Grammar
 - Complete math operators and symbols supported
- Implementation in new areas
 - Math areas, Physics, Technology...
- More languages
 - Currently, Spanish and Catalan.

Mathematical notation on the web: locution

- PDF and other non Math-ML resources
- Better human voice than speech synthesizer
- The technological possibilities to digitalize the human voice and store in files like MP3 format
- The possibility of enclose the files of sound to web texts

Mathematical notation on the web: locutions (RODOLFO Project)

How does it work?

1. Click on the formula
2. Locution is heard
3. The formula is locuted quite in real time!

3. Transitiva: $\forall x, y, z \in A : xRy, yRz \Rightarrow xRz$ ya que $x^2 + x = y^2 + y$ $y^2 + y = z^2 + z$
entonces $x^2 + x = z^2 + z$

Toda relación de equivalencia define una partición en clases de equivalencia. Se llama **clase de equivalencia** de un elemento $a \in A$ al conjunto de todos los elementos de A que están relacionados con a .

$$[a] = \{x \in A / aRx\} \text{ (otra notación para } [a] \text{ es } \bar{a})$$

Mathematical notation on the web: A repository of locutions - RODOLFO

<http://cimanet.uoc.edu/rdf/>

Codi LaTeX

a \in A

Codi MathML-P

```
<math><mi>a</mi><mo>&Element;</mo><mi>A</mi></math>
```

Locució

Idioma	Transcripció	MP3
es	El elemento a pertenece al conjunto A	MP3
ca	L'element A pertany al conjunt A	MP3
ca	a pertany al conjunt A	MP3
ca	a pertany a A	MP3
es	El elemento A pertenece al conjunto A	MP3
es	a pertenece al conjunto A	MP3
es	a pertenece a A	MP3

Open repository for digital resources

- ❑ Many disseminated learning objects in the virtual campus
 - Need to be organized for searching and re-usability
 - Open access, restricted administration and authoring
 - Multilingual
 - Descriptors:
 - Dublin Core metadata standards (Dspace)
 - JEM Repository Taxonomy extended
 - JEM Type of Resources recommended tax
 - Key words

- ❑ Collaborative creation of new LO
 - Creative commons licence
 - Tagging (near future)

Open repository for digital resources

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <http://oer.uoc.edu/>. The page displays the UOC logo and navigation menu on the left. The main content area shows a search result for an exercise titled "Ejercicio". The metadata includes:

- Título:** Ejercicio
- Autor:** FUOC
- Palabras clave:** ANOVA, p-valor, Hipótesis nula, Análisis de variancia, Error estimación
- Fecha de publicación:** 4-may-2009
- URI:** <http://hdl.handle.net/10489/73>
- Aparece en las colecciones:** Recursos d'aprenentatge d'estadística / Recursos de aprendizaje de estadística / Statistics learning resource

Below the metadata, there is a table of files:

Fichero	Descripción	Tamaño	Formato
UOC_00000031_ca.pdf		200.17 kB	Adobe PDF Visualizar/Abrir

At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the Spanish Ministry of Education and Science, the Catalan Government, and the UOC.

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Automatic tutorials: learning and assessment (Logic course)

- ❑ Distance students are always alone
 - Logic courses students need continuous feedback
- ❑ Automatic tutorials are one solution
 - Well known experiences: students do not use them if they are not part of the assessment
- ❑ Automatic tutorial for learning and assessment of Logic is the SELL Project

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Automatic tutorials: learning and assessment (Logic course)

Castellano · Català

UOC Asistente E-Learning Lógica

Logica Enunciados · Deducción natural · Salir _USU_NOMBRE

Deducción natural en Lógica de enunciados

Ejercicios propuestos

Ejercicio

Mis ejercicios

Resumen

Ejercicios propuestos	
Correctos	
Incompletos	
Pendientes	

Ejercicios propios	
Correctos	
Incompletos	

Mis soluciones

Ejercicio	Tipo	Fecha	Estado	Crear

39

Automatic tutorials: learning and assessment (Logic course)

Castellano · Català

UOC Asistente E-Learning Lógica

Logica Enunciados · Deducción natural · Salir _USU_NOMBRE

Deducción natural en Lógica de enunciados

Ejercicios propuestos

Ejercicio

Mis ejercicios

Resumen

Ejercicios propuestos	
Correctos	
Incompletos	
Pendientes	

Ejercicios propios	
Correctos	
Incompletos	

Mis soluciones

Ejercicio	Tipo	Fecha	Estado	Crear

40

Thank you!

41

Thank you JEM!

<http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/search/node/UOC>

3rd JEM Workshop
Barcelona, 31 Jan - 2 Feb, 2008

 UOC

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4 **Antonio F. Costa** **Mathematics in UNED and JEM**

We shall present several improvements in e-learning mathematics at UNED (Distance Spanish University) for which we have profited from cooperation with the JEM network. More concretely:

- Mathematical editors for the platform Alf (e-learning platform of UNED)
- Remote Java laboratories
- Establishment of collaborations with other iberian distance universities: UOC (Catalunya) and Universidade Aberta (Portugal)

Mathematics in UNED

The UNED logo consists of the letters 'UNED' in a white, bold, sans-serif font, centered within a dark green square.

and JEM

J.A. Bujalance, A.F. Costa and A. M. Porto
JEM meeting
Aachen 21 August 2009

UNED

- Spanish distance University
- Founded in 1975
- 150.000 students
- Degree, master and Ph.D. in mathematics
- From classical distance learning to e-learning

The UNED logo consists of the letters 'UNED' in a white, bold, sans-serif font, centered within a dark green square.

UNED

Mathematical editor for the e-learning platform of UNED

Remote Java laboratories

Collaboration with other Iberian distance universities: UOC and Universidade Aberta

Mathematical editor for the e-learning platform of UNED

- E-learning Platform of UNED:
aLF (based on .LRN)
- Mathematical editor: Wiris Editor
Wiris Editor (**MATHS FOR MORE**)

Wiris Editor in aLF

- An example

Remote Java laboratories

- Easy Java Simulator:
www.um.es/fem/Ejs/
- Tutorial in JEM meeting in Trondheim
- Remote Java Laboratory for curves:
www.mat.uned.es/GeoCM/2PP/lab_curva

Collaboration between iberian distance universities

- Universidade Aberta (Portugal)
- Universitat Oberta Catalunya, UOC (Catalunya)
- UNED

- Workshop:

Matemática a distancia no contexto ibérico

Lisboa, June 24-26

UNIVERSIDADE
AbERTA
PORTUGAL, UNIVERSIDADE PÚBLICA DE ENSINO A DISTÂNCIA
www.univ-ab.pt
EM QUALQUER LUGAR DO MUNDO

MATEMÁTICA A DISTÂNCIA NO CONTEXTO IBÉRICO

24 a 26 de Junho

ORGANIZAÇÃO
Fernando Costa (Universidade Aberta, Lisboa)
Antonio Costa (Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Madrid)
Maria Antonia Huertas (Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Barcelona)

Universidade Aberta
Palácio Ceia
Rua da Escola Politécnica, 147
Lisboa

Informações e contactos
<http://www.univ-ab.pt/mdci1/>

ABERTA UNED UOC

Some of the purposes

- Erasmus agreement for students and staff mobility
- Participation in direction of degree thesis and master thesis
- Ph. D. common program
- Participation in common courses for teachers formation
- Submission of research common projects to obtain financial support
- Organization of a workshop every year: next one in Madrid
- Invitation to Ibero-american distance universities

JEM:

Joining
Educational
Mathematics

Thanks

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5 Hans Cuypers, Jan Willem Knopper, Hans Sterk

MESS: the MathDox Exercise System

Within MathDox, an open source system for presenting highly interactive mathematical documents over the world wide web, we have developed an exercise system. This exercise system consists of an XML-format for interactive mathematical exercises, a player of these exercises and tools for using the exercises inside Learning Management Systems. We discuss the features of our system by way of an extended example.

MESS: the MathDox Exercise System

Hans Cuypers, Jan Willem Knopper, Hans Sterk

Abstract. Within MathDox [4, 5], an open source system for presenting highly interactive mathematical documents over the world wide web, we have developed an exercise system. This exercise system consists of an XML-format for interactive mathematical exercises, a player of these exercises and tools for using the exercises inside Learning Management Systems. We discuss the features of our system by way of an extended example.

Keywords. adaptivity, interactive mathematical documents, Math assistants, tutoring and assessment systems.

1. Introduction

In the area of Mathematics we see that quite recently various new tools have been created which offer students a rich environment for practicing mathematics over the world wide web. These systems offer parametrized exercises with open questions that are automatically graded. Indeed, Maple TA (www.maplesoft.com), Aleks (www.aleks.com), MyMathLab (www.mymathlab.com) and WebAssign (www.webassign.net) are commercial systems offering this type of facilities, while WIMS (wims.unice.fr) and WebWORK (webwork.math.rochester.edu) are some open source initiatives in this direction. The feedback that these systems provide, however, is usually very restricted. STACK (www.stack.bham.ac.uk), DWO (www.fi.uu.nl/dwo) and the LeActiveMath (www.leactivemath.org) system, are systems for mathematical exercises offering more intelligent feedback, see [6, 7] and [8]. Here we report on our own initiatives to create an interactive exercise system as part of our system MathDox (www.mathdox.org), which is capable of providing valuable feedback going beyond the correct/incorrect reply.

MathDox is a system serving dynamic and interactive webpages with high quality rendering of mathematics and easy access to mathematical services like computer algebra systems or dynamic geometry software, see [4, 5]. MathDox shows its potential when demonstrating the workings of an algorithm or explaining new concepts with dynamic on-screen calculations. One of the key features of MathDox, making the above possible, is the semantic encoding of mathematical expressions by OpenMath.

In this paper we focus on some features of the MathDox system and, in particular, we explain how these features have been used to create a rich environment, called MESS (MathDox Exercise SyStem) for parametrized mathematical exercises providing easy access to all kinds of mathematical (web)services, taking care of good presentation of mathematics, offering easy and natural input of mathematics, and of facilities to provide meaningful feedback to users. In particular, we will demonstrate how we make use of the semantic encoding of mathematical expressions with OpenMath.

Participating in the JEM network gave us a good opportunity to learn and discuss initiatives in educational mathematics, and partly shaped the MESS.

2. The MathDox exercise format

MathDox sources combine in a modular way various existing XML formats best suited for our purposes. Each format contributes a useful facet for interactive documents. The main XML formats used in MathDox exercises are: LEAMEL, the LeActiveMath Exercise Language [3]; OpenMath, for semantic encoding of mathematics; Jelly, a programming and scripting format. These formats, their use and purpose, will now be discussed. LEAMEL is the main format for a MathDox exercise. It captures the structure of an exercise.

A MathDox exercise can be considered to be an automaton. The various states of the automaton, called *interactions*, are presented by the MathDox player as webpages to the user. These interactions may contain the question of an exercise, the feedback on a correct or wrong answer and some hints. The transitions from one state into another, called *answer maps*, are ruled by the actions of the user, and the results of various queries to mathematical services available within the exercise. We explain this by way of the following example: Determine $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$. This is the question of the exercise, it is the first state of the automaton that the user will encounter when starting up the exercise. Now the user may provide an answer, correct or incorrect. For each of these two possibilities the exercise contains an interaction, that the user will visit after supplying his answer. This exercise can be encoded in the XML-exercise format.

```
<exercise>
  <interaction id='question'>
    <para>Determine
      <OMOBJ>
        <OMA><OMS name='plus' cd='arith1' />
          <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
            <OMI>1</OMI><OMI>4</OMI>
          </OMA>
          <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
            <OMI>1</OMI><OMI>6</OMI>
          </OMA>
        </OMOBJ>
      </para>
    <para>
      <userinput type='blank'><set name='answer'></userinput>
    </para>
    <answer_map>
      <choose>
        <when target='correct'>
          <query>
            <OMOBJ>
              <OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
```

```

<out name='answer' />
<OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
  <OMI>5</OMI><OMI>12</OMI>
</OMA>
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>
</query>
</when>
<otherwise target='incorrect' />
</choose>
</answer_map>
</interaction>
<interaction id='correct'>
  <para>Well done!</para>
</interaction>

<interaction id='incorrect'>
  <para>Sorry, that is wrong.</para>
<answer_map text='Try again'>
  <interaction xref='question' />
</answer_map>
</interaction>
</exercise>

```

The question is posed in the interaction with id equal to `question`. In that interaction one also finds a `userinput`-tag. This tag represents an input field for the user. Inside the webpage representing this interaction, the `userinput`-tag is replaced by the MathDox-formula editor, see Figure 1. The answer of the user is set to the variable with name `answer`. In the `answer_map` at the end of the interaction, a query (to for example a Computer Algebra System) is defined that checks whether the answer is equal to $5/12$. This `answer_map` redirects the user either to the interaction with id `correct` or the interaction with id `incorrect`. The latter interaction offers the possibility to try the exercise again.

The mathematics inside the exercise is encoded in OpenMath, a format for semantically rich encoding of mathematics. Within MathDox mathematics appears in various forms: Mathematics as used in computations by software packages or mathematics solely meant for the user to read or sometimes for both the computer and the user. For each type of usage one wants the mathematics to have specific properties. In general a user will be able to grasp the meaning behind a, possibly ambiguous, mathematical expression, often helped by the context in which the expression appears. Computer software, however, will need its mathematics to be completely unambiguous, since it cannot benefit from the context in the way a mathematically skilled reader does in order to solve gaps caused by incompleteness and ambiguity.

OpenMath has been chosen as the main format for mathematics within MathDox documents. It is well suited because it is semantically rich, unambiguous, XML-based and can easily be transformed into other formats, such as MathML and \LaTeX , which are better suited for presentation. These transformations allow MathDox documents to use OpenMath where semantics is important and switch to MathML or \LaTeX , when the mathematics needs to be presented to the user either on screen or on paper.

Determine $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$.

FIGURE 1. Exercise in MESS

To give the reader an idea of the OpenMath encoding of the semantics of a mathematical expression, we analyze the snippet of OpenMath representing $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$:

```
<OMOBJ>
  <OMA><OMS name='plus' cd='arith1' />
    <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
      <OMI>1</OMI><OMI>4</OMI>
    </OMA>
    <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
      <OMI>1</OMI><OMI>6</OMI>
    </OMA>
  </OMA>
</OMOBJ>
```

In this encoding we find an application (OMA) of a symbol (OMS) with name `plus` and defined in a so-called content dictionary (cd) with the name `arith1` being applied to the two fractions. Each fraction consists of an application of the symbol `divide` to two integers (OMI). The semantics of this expression is hidden in the attributes `name` and `cd`. Indeed, the content dictionaries contain the semantical information of the various symbols. They are provided with the document.

The semantic information available from the OpenMath expressions enables easy translations between OpenMath and application specific syntax. At the moment MathDox supports interaction with various mathematical (web)services such as the computer algebra systems Mathematica, Maple, GAP, Maxima, Wiris, Magma and Singular, and the dynamic geometry systems Geogebra and Cinderella.

Interoperability between these systems is achieved by making use of so-called OpenMath phrasebooks. For each of the forementioned systems there is a separate OpenMath phrasebook (Caprotti, Cohen & Riem [1]) that handles the translation from OpenMath to the computer algebra system language and back.

The types of possible computations are only limited by what the computer algebra systems are capable of performing and what the OpenMath phrasebooks will be able to translate. However, the phrasebooks also allow for communication in the application's specific syntax.

To specify and fine-tune reactions of a MathDox document to user input, an author needs programming constructs. For this purpose Jelly¹ has been included in the MathDox format. Jelly is a JSP-like XML-language². Jelly can be used for conditional statements, loops, variables, calls to Java objects and calls to web services. The specific use of Jelly in exercises will be explained in the examples in the following sections.

3. MathDox software

So far we have only discussed the MathDox Exercise format and just briefly mentioned the server-side software responsible for processing of this format. In this section we discuss the MathDox software.

The MathDox Player is responsible for making MathDox documents accessible over the web. Its task is similar to that of a web server in the sense that both a web-server and the MathDox Player offer stored documents from the server to the outside world.

¹<http://commons.apache.org/jelly>

²<http://java.sun.com/products/jsp>

The main difference between a normal web-server and the MathDox Player is that a web-server offers ready-made HTML files, whereas the MathDox Player dynamically creates these HTML files. On request of the user the MathDox server collects data from the source document, the user and from mathematical backengines providing services, and creates, by applying a number of XSL transformations on this input, a new view on the document.

Collecting data and converting the MathDox source together with the input of the user and backengines into presentable HTML pages is the main task of the MathDox Player. To enable the users of MathDox documents to interact with the system, HTML offers various options, like buttons, text areas and links. However, there is no standard way to communicate mathematics in a meaningful way. Especially, since we want to enable the interaction with various mathematical services offered by the system, we require the user to provide semantically rich mathematical expressions. To this end we have developed a formula editor featuring:

- a two-dimensional WYSIWYM (what you see is what you mean) interface.
- semantic representation of the formulae in OpenMath.

The editor is written in Javascript and can easily be integrated in HTML web pages.

4. How to handle student answers

Mathdox exercises consist of various **interactions**. A crucial part in these exercises is the transition between these various **interactions**. As explained above these transitions are ruled by the **answer_maps**, and depend on various parameters, including student answers to the questions posed in the exercises.

In the example of Section 2, we have encountered the exercise ‘Determine $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$ ’. The query

```
<query>
  <OMOBJ>
    <OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
      <out name='answer' />
      <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
        <OMI>5</OMI><OMI>12</OMI>
      </OMA>
    </OMOBJ>
  </query>
```

where **answer** is the name of the variable in which the answer to this question is posed, is used to decide whether the answer is correct or not.

This query is shipped to a mathematical service, and evaluated. If the response is **True** the student has passed the exercise, if not he has failed it. The default service used by MESS is a Computer Algebra System, e.g. Mathematica or Maxima.

Although at first sight this seems to be a good way to proceed, there is a lot of ambiguity in this approach.

We mention some problems. If the student supplies the answer $\frac{5}{12}$, then the query returns **True**; but this will also be the case when the student answers $\frac{10}{24}$, and also when he answer $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$. Maybe, the second answer, $\frac{10}{24}$, is acceptable, but the third, $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$,

certainly not. In general, a CAS will reply **True** when testing equality of these possible answers with $\frac{5}{12}$.

A similar problem occurs when we ask a student to simplify the expression $\frac{x^4-1}{x^2-1}$ as far as possible. Student answers could be $\frac{x^4-1}{x^2-1}$, $\frac{x^3-x^2+x-1}{x-1}$, $1+x^2$ or x^2+1 . Here, the last two answers are probably the ones we would like to approve.

Of course, we can program the CAS in such a way that it only returns **True** in the desired situations. Although MESS allows for this approach, it is not the preferred way of handling this kind of problem. Indeed, it would involve too much of CAS-specific programming in an exercise, while our goal is to be as much independent of the choice of CAS as possible.

The systems STACK and LeActiveMath have attacked these problems by designing various types of equivalence checks, see [6, 8]. For example, in STACK one can distinguish the following equality checks for two objects (e.g. students answer and answer provided by the system):

CASEqual	Are the parse trees of the two expressions equal
Equal_com_ass	Are they equal up to commutativity and associativity of elementary arithmetic operations? E.g. $a + b = b + a$, but $x + x \neq 2x$.
AlgEquiv	Are they algebraically equivalent, i.e. does the difference simplify to zero within the CAS used?
SubstEquiv	Can we find a substitution of the variables of ex2 into ex1 which renders ex1 algebraically equivalent to ex2?
SameType	Are the two expressions of the same type? Note that this test works recursively over the entire expression.

LeActiveMath provides similar checks. These equality checks cover a lot of cases, but certainly not all.

What do we do when a student provides a complete computation instead of just the final answer?

Or suppose one asks the student to write the gcd of 111 and 93 as a linear combination of 111 and 93. In this case you expect an answer in the form $a \cdot 111 + b \cdot 93 = \text{gcd}(111, 93)$, where a and b are integers. But how do we check correctness?

As a (partial) solution to these problems MathDox use of XPath functionalities in Jelly. These functionalities enable us to inspect the student's answer in similar ways as is done in STACK, but offers more flexibility.

For example, suppose the student provides an answer to the question of determining $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}$, and this answer is an OpenMath expression set in the variable `answer`. Then we want the answer only to involve integers and division. The XPath-test

```
<!-- if select="$answer//OMS[not(@name='divide' and @cd='arith1')]"/>
```

tells us whether there is any other OpenMath symbol, different from

```
<!-- OMS name='divide' cd='arith' />
```

in the student's answer. If we encounter another symbol, then we can report this to the student and ask him to provide an answer only involving integers and division.

In answering the second question on simplifying $\frac{x^4-1}{x^2-1}$, we might test the student's answer to be equal to $x^2 + 1$ by not only using a query that checks equality up to algebraic equivalence (using a CAS) but also performing a check on the absence of the divide symbol:

```
<if select="not($answer//OMS[@name='divide' and @cd='arith1'])"/>
```

These XPath tools also give us the possibility to select various parts out of an OpenMath expression. For example, if the student answer equals the OpenMath expression

```
<OMOBJ>
  <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
    <OMI>a</OMI><OMI>b</OMI>
  </OMA>
</OMOBJ>
```

where **a** and **b** are two integers, then with

```
<set name='enumerator'>
  <copyOf select='$answer//OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=1]' />
</set>

<set name='denominator'>
  <copyOf select='$answer//OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=2]' />
</set>
```

we can select the enumerator and denominator of **answer**. They can now be checked individually to be equal to 5 and 12, respectively.

Moreover, using XPath makes it possible to have a student provide a computation like

$$\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6} = \frac{3}{12} + \frac{2}{12} = \frac{5}{12}.$$

With XPath we can chop this computation into

$$\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6} = \frac{3}{12} + \frac{2}{12} \text{ and } \frac{3}{12} + \frac{2}{12} = \frac{5}{12}$$

and check each of these equations separately.

As a final example we mention that with XPath we can also analyse an answer like $-5 \cdot 111 + 6 \cdot 93 = 3$ to write the gcd of 111 and 93 as a linear combination of 111 and 93. Indeed, we can select both left and right hand side of the equality and check that they are equal to $\text{gcd}(111, 93)$. Moreover, we can check that one of the sides is an integer, and the other side is a linear combination of 111 and 93.

These kinds of XPath operations provide powerful tools to analyse student's answers, do type checking, test for forbidden symbols, and select subexpressions for further computation.

5. MESS at work in an example

In this section we will illustrate the possibilities of MESS by an extended example. We continue with the exercise as described above: add two fractions. However, now we use some more of the facilities offered by MathDox to create a more interactive exercise, which provides the student with useful feedback. First generalize the question by parametrizing it. For this purpose we add the new randomized parameters **a**, **b**, **c** and **d** to the first interaction and introduce the variables with names **sum** and **answer**.

```

<interaction id='question'>
<random var='a' minimum='1' maximum='9' /> <random var='b' minimum='3' maximum='9' />
<random var='c' minimum='1' maximum='9' /> <random var='d' minimum='3' maximum='9' />
<set name='sum'>
<OMOBJ><OMA><OMS cd='arith1' name='plus' />
<OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
<OMI>${a}</OMI><OMI>${b}</OMI>
</OMA>
<OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
<OMI>${c}</OMI><OMI>${d}</OMI>
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>
</set>

<set name='answer'>
<OMOBJ> <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
<OMV name='a' /><OMV name='b' />
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>
</set>

<para>Determine <out name='sum' />.</para>
<para>Provide your answer in the form <math>\frac{a}{b}</math>.</para>
<para>
<out name='sum' />=<userinput type='blank'>
<set name='answer'><OMOBJ><out name='answer' /></OMOBJ></set>
</userinput>
</para>

<answer_map text='check your answer'> ... </answer_map>
</interaction>

```

This results in a randomized question. Next we want to extend the responses on a student's answer. Besides the correct and incorrect feedback, we can also provide the following types of feedback: If the answer is not fully simplified (i.e., the gcd of the numerator and denominator is not equal to 1) we provide the following feedback:

```

<interaction id='almost'>
<para> Indeed, <out name='answer' /> equals <out name='sum' />, but maybe you can simplify your answer a bit. </para>
<answer_map text='Try again'>
<interaction xref='question' />
</answer_map>
</interaction>

```

Determine $\frac{2}{8} + \frac{8}{5}$.

Provide your answer in the form $\frac{a}{b}$.

$$\frac{2}{8} + \frac{8}{5} = \frac{\text{a}}{\text{b}}$$

Indeed, $\frac{74}{40}$ equals $\frac{2}{8} + \frac{8}{5}$, but maybe you can simplify your answer a bit.

FIGURE 2. A randomized exercise and feedback

Another useful type of feedback is feedback on common mistakes, referred to as 'buggy rules'. A common buggy rule for adding fractions is the addition both the numerators and denominators. If a student provides such an answer, then the exercise replies with the following feedback.

```

<interaction id='buggy'>
  <para>Oops, did you add the denominators and enumerators? This is not allowed.</para>
  <para>You first have to make the denominators equal and then add the two fractions by adding the enumerators.</para>
  <answer_map text='Try again'>
    <interaction xref='question' />
  </answer_map>
</interaction>

```

Having added these interactions, it remains to specify the `answer_map` in the question-interaction. This `answer_map` will have the following structure:

```

<choose>
  <when target='correct'> ...</when>
  <when target='buggy'> ...</when>
  <otherwise target='incorrect' />
</choose>

```

Each `<when/>`-tag contains a query involving the student's answer to a CAS resulting in either a `True` or `False`. The user is redirected to the first target for which this query yields a `True`. For the `correct`-target we have to analyze the student's answer. Indeed, we check that the answer is a fraction not only equal to the expected answer, but that the gcd of the numerator and denominator is equal to 1. Here we make use of the XML-structure of the answer:

```

<OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
  <OMV name='a' />
  <OMV name='b' />
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>

```

With the Jelly-command

```
<copyOf select='$answer//OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=1]' />
```

we can select the first sibling of the divide symbol, i.e., we get the numerator of the fraction. Similarly

```
<copyOf select='$answer//OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=2]' />
```

provides us with the denominator. We use this in the following query that checks correctness of the answer, and whether it is in simplified form.

```

<query>
<OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='and' cd='logic1' />
  <OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
    <out name='answer' /><out name='sum' />
  </OMA>
  <OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
    <OMA><OMS name='gcd' cd='arith1' />
      <copyOf select='$answer//OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=1]' />
      <copyOf select='$answer//OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=2]' />
    </OMA>
  <OMI>1</OMI>
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>
</query>

```

Now the second `<when/>`-tag can be filled with

```

<query>
<OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
  <out name='answer' /><out name='sum' />
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>
</query>

```

while the target `buggy` will be chosen if the following query yields a `True`.

```

<query>
<OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
  <out name='answer' />
  <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
    <OMI>${a+c}</OMI><OMI>${b+d}</OMI>
  </OMA>
</OMA>
</OMOBJ>

```

</query>

This results in the following XML-encoding of the complete exercise.

```

<exercise>
  <interaction id='question'>
    <if test='{ft ne 'false'}'>
      <random var='a' minimum='1' maximum='9' /> <random var='b' minimum='3' maximum='9' />
      <random var='c' minimum='1' maximum='9' /> <random var='d' minimum='3' maximum='9' />
      <set name='sum'>
        <OMOBJ><OMA><OMS cd='arith1' name='plus' />
          <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
            <OMI>${a}</OMI><OMI>${b}</OMI>
          </OMA>
          <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
            <OMI>${c}</OMI><OMI>${d}</OMI>
          </OMA>
        </OMA>
      </OMOBJ>
    </set>
    <set name='answer'>
      <OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
        <OMV name='a' /><OMV name='b' />
      </OMA>
    </OMOBJ>
  </set>
</if>
<set var='ft'>false</c:set>

<para>Determine <out name='sum' />.</para>
<para>Provide your answer in the form <math>\frac{a}{b}</math>.</para>
<para><out name='sum' />=<userinput type='blank'>
  <set name='answer'><OMOBJ><out name='answer' /></OMOBJ></set>
  </userinput></para>

<answer_map text='check your answer'>
  <choose>
    <when target='correct'>
      <query>
        <OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='and' cd='logic1' />
          <OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
            <out name='answer' />
            <out name='sum' />
          </OMA>
          <OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
            <OMA><OMS name='gcd' cd='arith1' />
              <copyOf select='${answer}/om:OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=1]' />
              <copyOf select='${answer}/om:OMS[@name='divide']/following-sibling::*[position()=2]' />
            </OMA>
            <OMI>1</OMI>
          </OMA>
        </OMOBJ>
      </query>
    </when>

    <when target='almost'>
      <query>
        <OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
          <out name='answer' /><out name='sum' />
        </OMA>
      </OMOBJ>
    </query>
  </when>

    <when target='buggy'>
      <query>
        <OMOBJ><OMA><OMS name='eq' cd='relation1' />
          <out name='answer' />
          <OMA><OMS name='divide' cd='arith1' />
            <OMI>${a+c}</OMI><OMI>${b+d}</OMI>
          </OMA>
        </OMA>
      </OMOBJ>
    </query>
  </when>
</choose>
</when target='correct'>

```

```

</when>
<otherwise target='incorrect'/>
</choose>
</answer_map>
</interaction>

<interaction id='correct'>
<para>Well done!</para>
<answer_map text='Try a new exercise'>
  <set var='ft'>true</c:set>
  <interaction xref='question'/>
</answer_map>
</interaction>

<interaction id='almost'>
<para>Indeed, <out name='answer'/> equals <out name='sum'/>, but maybe you can simplify your answer a bit.</para>
<answer_map text='Try again'>
  <interaction xref='question'/>
</answer_map>
</interaction>

<interaction id='buggy'>
<para>Oops, did you add the denominators and enumerators? This is not allowed.</para>
<para>You first have to make the denominators equal and then add the two fractions by adding the enumerators.</para>
<answer_map text='Try again'>
  <interaction xref='question'/>
</answer_map>
</interaction>

<interaction id='incorrect'>
<para>Sorry, that is wrong!</para>
<answer_map text='Try again'>
  <interaction xref='question'/>
</answer_map>
</interaction>
</exercise>

```

6. Organising courses with MESS

Despite the fact that MathDox and MESS can be used to create and play exercises, they are not intended or designed to be a Learning Management System (LMS) like Blackboard, Moodle, or Sakai. To enable the use of MathDox exercises in an LMS, we developed a scoring system and made it possible to include MathDox documents in SCORM (Sharable Content Object Reference Model)³ packages. In this way it is possible to use the facilities of these LMS to organise courses with MESS.

To facilitate the management of these SCORM packages, and the administration of the results of the students, it is possible to use the functionalities of the used LMS. But we do not rely on the LMS. Indeed, we have built a management system for the content and student administration, which enables users to create scorm content out of our database of exercises, attach them to various courses and get extended reports on the results of students on the exercises. This has been implemented in the project Wortel TU/e⁴, the mathematical web environment of the Technical University of Eindhoven, built upon MESS and Moodle. Here one finds also a collection of about 1000 parametrized exercises in basic highschool math, undergraduate calculus, linear algebra, algebra and discrete mathematics.

³www.adlnet.gov/scorm

⁴wortel.tue.nl

7. Conclusions

The MathDox Exercise System MESS provides a very flexible and rich environment for mathematical problem solving. Besides offering easy access to various computer algebra systems, high quality rendering of mathematics in browsers, and a convenient mathematical input editor, it also provides many ways of giving immediate, meaningful and intelligent feedback on user's actions.

References

- [1] O. Caprotti, A.M. Cohen, A.M., Riem, M. , Java phrasebooks for Computer Algebra and Automated Deduction, Sigsam Bulletin (2000).
- [2] A.M. Cohen, H. Cuypers, E.R. Barreiro, H. Sterk, Interactive Mathematical Documents on the Web, in Algebra, Geometry and Software Systems (eds M. Joswig and N. Takayama), Springer Verlag, 289-306 (2003).
- [3] A. Cohen, H. Cuypers, D. Jibeteau, M. Spanbroek, LeActiveMath Exercise Language, Deliverable 7, LeActivemath, <http://www.leactivemath.org/publications1.html> (2004).
- [4] A.M. Cohen, H. Cuypers, E.R. Barreiro, MathDox : mathematical documents on the web. In M. Kohlhase (Ed.), OMDoc : An Open Markup Format for Mathematical Documents (pp. 262-265) Berlin: Springer-Verlag (2006).
- [5] A.M. Cohen, H. Cuypers, J.W. Knopper, M. Spanbroek, R. Verrijzer, MathDox - A System for Interactive Mathematics, in Proceedings of Ed-media, 5177-5182 (2008).
- [6] G. Gogvadze, A. G. Palomo, E. Melis, Interactivity of Exercises in ActiveMath Towards Sustainable and Scalable Educational Innovations Informed by the Learning Sciences Sharing. Good Practices of Research Experimentation and Innovation, Volume 133, Edited by Chee-Kit Looi, David Jonassen, Mitsuru Ikeda (2005).
- [7] E. Melis, J. Siekmann, ActiveMath: An Intelligent Tutoring System for Mathematics, in the proceedings of the Seventh International Conference 'Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing, LNAI 3070, 91-101, ed. L. Rutkowski, J. Siekmann, R. Tadeusiewicz, L.A. Zadeh, Springer Verlag (2004).
- [8] C. Sangwin, STACK: making many fine judgements rapidly (2007).

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6 Christine Müller and Michael Kohlhase Semantic Technologies for Mathematical eLearning

With the globalisation in education, bridging cultural differences by making course material more accessible and adaptable to individual user needs becomes an important goal. In this paper we attack this goal for the field of mathematics where knowledge is abstract, highly structured, and extraordinarily interlinked. Modern representation formats like our OMDoc format allow us to capture, model, relate, and represent mathematical learning objects and thus make them context-aware and machine-adaptable to the respective learning contexts. But to make mathematical knowledge accessible to learners of diverse cultural backgrounds we also need to model mathematical practice.

In this paper, we show that many practices of mathematical communities can already be modeled in OMDoc and outline extensions to support further ones. We have implemented a collection of services that allow applications to interpret and manage OMDoc and its practice representations. These services are integrated into our prototype eLearning platform to demonstrate how systems can improve the accessibility of mathematical eLearning materials.

Focus of the talk: Generation of exam according to the teacher's preferences (or context)

Semantic Technologies for Mathematical eLearning

A Semantic Exams Generator¹

Christine Müller and Michael Kohlhase

Department of Computer Science
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Presentation for the Final JEM Workshop

August 21, 2009

¹Special thanks go to Normen Müller.

Motivation: A Vision

- Digitalisation of learning resources
- Web-accessible eLearning repositories
- Collaborative, distributed authoring and enrichment of web resources
- Support for maintenance and consistency
- Personalised search and retrieval
- Interactions with eLearning material

Related Work

- Consistent creation of learning material from a collection of resources: CONNEXIONS [1]
- Interactive mathematical web pages: MATHDOX [2]
- Interactive Exercises with user-specific feedback: Heeren et al. [3], ACTIVEMATH [4], and MATHDOX
- Course generation according to learning goal and competence: ACTIVEMATH

Focus & Approach

Focus: Adaptation of semantically marked up documents for teachers.

- **Markup** of eLearning resources
- **Generating a template** from an eLearning document:
 $Doc \times Sel \Rightarrow Tmp$
- **Instantiating the template** according to the teacher's preferences:
 $Tmp \times Context \Rightarrow Doc$
- Case study: Exams generation

Outline

- 1 Document Markup
- 2 Template Generation
- 3 Exams Generation

Exam 2000

Exam 2000

Written by: Christine Müller

1. Graphs

EXERCISE (GRAPH PROBLEM 1):

This graph problem is very easy.

2. Trees

EXERCISE (TREE PROBLEM 1):

This tree problem is very easy.

3. Functions

EXERCISE (WHAT IS A FUNCTION?):

This is the standard function problem and should be in every exam that covers functions.

Classification of Text Fragments and Structure

Markup with XML

```

<?xml version="1.0"?>
<omdoc ...>
  <metadata>
    <dc:title>Exam 2000</dc:title>
    <dc:creator>Christine Müller</dc:creator>
  </metadata>
  <theory xml:id="exam00.t.g">
    <import from="...">
    <metadata><dc:title>Graphs</dc:title></metadata>
    <exercise xml:id="graph1.ex">
      <metadata>...</metadata>
      <CMP>This graph problem is very easy.</CMP>
    </exercise>
  </theory>
  <theory xml:id="exam00.t.t">
    <import from="...">
    <metadata><dc:title>Trees</dc:title></metadata>
    <exercise xml:id="tree1.ex">
      <metadata>...</metadata>
      <CMP>This tree problem is very easy.</CMP>
    </exercise>
  </theory>
  <theory xml:id="exam00.t.f">
    <import from="...">
    <metadata><dc:title>Functions</dc:title></metadata>
    <exercise xml:id="fun1.ex">
      <metadata>...</metadata>
      <CMP>This is the standard function problem ...</CMP>
    </exercise>
  </theory>
</omdoc>
  
```


Tree structure of Exam 2000

Exam 2000

Written by: Christine Müller

1. Graphs

EXERCISE (GRAPH PROBLEM 1):
This graph problem is very easy.

2. Trees

EXERCISE (TREE PROBLEM 1):
This tree problem is very easy.

3. Functions

EXERCISE (WHAT IS A FUNCTION?):
This is the standard function problem and should be in every exam that covers functions.

Markup of Dependencies

Dependency Graph of Exam 2000

Exam 2000

Written by: Christine Müller

1. Graphs

EXERCISE (GRAPH PROBLEM 1):

This graph problem is very easy.

2. Trees

EXERCISE (TREE PROBLEM 1):

This tree problem is very easy.

3. Functions

EXERCISE (WHAT IS A FUNCTION?):

This is the standard function problem and should be in every exam that covers functions.

Repository Graph

Outline

- 1 Document Markup
- 2 Template Generation
- 3 Exams Generation

A Smaller Example

Exam 2000

Written by: Christine Müller

1. Graphs

EXERCISE (GRAPH PROBLEM 1):
This graph problem is very easy.

- ▼ demo
 - ▼ exams
 - exam00.omdoc
 - ▼ graph
 - ▼ en
 - graph.omdoc
 - ▼ problems
 - graph1.omdoc
 - graph2.omdoc
 - graph3.omdoc

Document Abstraction

```

function abstract (d:Doc, s:Sel): Doc =
  tmp:Doc = ( $\emptyset$ ,  $\emptyset$ )
  sel:V = apply(s,d)
  forall v  $\in$  V(d)
    if v  $\in$  sel then
      var:Node =  $\varepsilon$ 
      ref:Edge = (var,reference,v)
      tmp + ({var},{ref})
    else
      tmp + ({v},{Ev(d)})
  return tmp

```


Generating a Template from Exam 2000


```

<omdoc ...>
  <metadata><dc:title>Exam 2000</dc:title></metadata>
  <theory xml:id="exam00.t">
    <import from="..." />
    <metadata>
      <dc:title>Graphs</dc:title>
    </metadata>
    <exercise>
      <metadata><dc:title>The graph problem</dc:title></metadata>
    </exercise>
  </theory>
</omdoc>

```

```

<omdoc ...>
  <metadata><dc:title>Exam Template</dc:title></metadata>
  <theory xml:id="exam-abs.t">
    <import from="..." />
    <metadata>
      <dc:title>Graphs</dc:title>
    </metadata>
    <variant>
      <ref xref="exam00.omdoc/./[1]/[1]/[4]/[2]"/>
    </variant>
  </theory>
</omdoc>

```


Outline

- 1 Document Markup
- 2 Template Generation
- 3 Exams Generation

Document Concretion

```

function concretise (tmp:Doc, ac:AC, db: Doc): Doc =
  db import tmp
  d:Doc = ( $\emptyset$ ,  $\emptyset$ )
  forall v  $\in$  V(tmp)
    if v is a variant then
      d + (db findVariant for  $ac_v$ )
    else d + ( $\{v\}$ ,  $E_v(ad)$ )
  return d

```


Guiding the Concretion

Users can guide the concretion by defining a **set of constraints** for variant node in the template. This is called the **adaptation context**.

We illustrate the concretion with the following adaptation context:

- Omit all problems in exam 1999,
- Include the function problem “fun1.ex”,
- The problems should be harder than exam 2000,
- The older the problems the better.

Graph Representation of the Adaptation Context


```
digraph "exam 2009" {
  "exam 2009";
  /* the older the better */
  "exercises for exam 2009" [xpath="exam09.omdoc//exercise",age=max];
  "exam 2009" -> "exercises for exam 2009" [type="contains"];
  /* omit problems in exam 1999 */
  "exam 1999" [xpath="exam99.omdoc"];
  "exam 1999" -> "exercises for exam 2009" [type="!contains"];
  /* include the function problem */
  "fun1.ex" [xpath="fun/problems/fun1.omdoc/./[1]/[1]/[2]"];
  "exam 2009" -> "fun1.ex" [type="contains"];
  /* problems should be harder than exam 2000 */
  "exam 2000" [xpath="exam00.omdoc"];
  "exam 2009" -> "exam 2000" [type="more-difficult-than"];
  ...
}
```


Omit all Problems in Exam 1999

More difficult than Exam 2000

Select one Graph Problem

Select all Problems

From Exam 2000 to Exam 2009

Exam 2000

Written by: Christine Müller

1. Graphs

EXERCISE (GRAPH PROBLEM 1):

This graph problem is very easy.

2. Trees

EXERCISE (TREE PROBLEM 1):

This tree problem is very easy.

3. Functions

EXERCISE (WHAT IS A FUNCTION?):

This is the standard function problem and should be in every exam that covers functions.

Exam 2009

Written by: Adaptor

1. Graphs

EXERCISE (THE GRAPH PROBLEM 3):

This problem on graphs is very difficult.

2. Trees

EXERCISE (TREE PROBLEM 3):

This is the tree problem 3. It is very difficult.

3. Function

EXERCISE (WHAT IS A FUNCTION?):

This is the standard problem and should be in every exam that covers functions.

Summary

Focus: Adaptation of semantically marked up documents for teachers.

- **Markup** of eLearning resources
- **Generating a template** from an eLearning document:
 $Doc \times Sel \Rightarrow Tmp$
- **Instantiating the template** according to the teacher's preferences:
 $Tmp \times Context \Rightarrow Doc$
- Case study: Exams generation

Thank you! Questions?

For Further Reading I

R.G. Baraniuk, C.S. Burrus, B.M. Hendricks, G.L. Henry, A.O. Hero III, D.H. Johnson, D.L. Jones, J. Kusuma, R.D. Nowak, J.E. Odegard, L.C. Potter, K. Ramchandran, R.J. Reedstrom, P. Schniter, I.W. Selesnick, D.B. Williams, and W.L. Wilson.

ConneXions: DSP education for a networked world.

In *Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 2002. Proceedings. (ICASSP '02). IEEE International Conference on*, volume 4 of *ICASSP Conference Proceedings*, pages 4144–4147. IEEE, 2002.

Hans Cuypers, Arjeh M. Cohen, Jan Willem Knopper, Rikko Verrijzer, and Mark Spanbroek.

MathDox, a system for interactive Mathematics.

In *Proceedings of World Conference on Educational Multimedia, Hypermedia and Telecommunications 2008*, pages 5177–5182, Vienna, Austria, June 2008. AACE.

Bastiaan Heeren, Johan Jeuring, Arthur van Leeuwen, and Alex Gerdes.

Specifying Strategies for Exercises.

In Serge Autexier, John Campbell, Julio Rubio, Volker Sorge, Masakazu Suzuki, and Freek Wiedijk, editors, *Intelligent Computer Mathematics, 9th International Conference, AISC 2008 15th Symposium, Calculemus 2008 7th International Conference, MKM 2008 Birmingham, UK, July 28 - August 1, 2008, Proceedings*, number 5144 in LNAI, pages 430–445. Springer Verlag, 2008.

E. Melis and J. Siekmann.

Activemath: An intelligent tutoring system for mathematics.

In *Seventh International Conference 'Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing' (ICAISC)*, volume 3070 of LNAI, pages 91–101. Springer-Verlag, 2004.

Semantic Technologies for Mathematical eLearning^{*}

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Abstract. With the globalisation in education, bridging cultural differences by making course material more accessible and adaptable to individual user needs becomes an important goal. In this paper we attack this goal for the field of mathematics where knowledge is abstract, highly structured, and extraordinary interlinked. Modern representation formats like our OMDOC format allow us to capture, model, relate, and represent mathematical learning objects and thus make them *context-aware* and *machine-adaptable* to the respective learning contexts. But to make mathematical knowledge accessible to learners of diverse cultural backgrounds we also need to model mathematical practice. In this paper, we show that many practices of mathematical communities can already be modeled in OMDOC and outline extensions to support further ones. We have implemented a collection of services that allow applications to interpret and manage OMDOC and its practice representations. These services are integrated into our prototype eLearning platform to demonstrate how systems can improve the accessibility of mathematical eLearning materials.

1 Introduction

With the ever-increasing globalisation of higher education, learning institutions have to cope with culturally induced differences in prerequisite knowledge and learning practices. This is especially pronounced at Jacobs University Bremen with an international student body: 1100 students from 88 countries on April 8th, 2008 [31].

Surprisingly, this also affects subjects like Mathematics and Computer Science that are often considered culture-independent. Even though most of our students are well prepared and possess good mathematical knowledge, a needs assessment study [1] shows mathematical discrepancies. Students of our one-year, introductory course on Computer Science (GenCS) reported that they had

^{*} This work was supported by JEM-Thematic-Network ECP-038208.

problems to get acquainted with the professor's notation systems, some had the feeling that the pace of the course was inappropriate and determined by the best students, some felt embarrassed to ask questions, while others did not face any problems and were able to balance out based on their previous education. Most students rate these discrepancies as problematic and believe that they can be associated with different educational and cultural backgrounds. In particular Romanian and Bulgarian students are very confident with their mathematical skills. Indian students are mostly well-educated in programming languages. Other nationalities struggle with the course. We assume that our students are capable of passing the course, but eventually give up when they are not able to map their previous mathematical background and practices to our course. In this situation, we want to augment lectures with online material that can be adapted to individual user needs.

We claim that the theory of *communities of practice* [17] can help us understand different mathematical practices and backgrounds and to eventually counteract pre-existing differences. According to Lave and Wenger [17], communities of practice (CoPs) are groups of people who *share an interest* in a particular domain — in our case the interest in the GenCS course. By interacting and collaborating around problems, solutions, and insights they *develop shared practices*, i.e. a common repertoire of resources consisting of experiences, stories, tools, and ways of addressing recurring problems. Even though mathematical practitioners seem to form a homogeneous, unified community and share the same practices all over the world, they actually form various sub-communities that differ in their preferred notations, basic mathematical assumptions, and motivating examples. We can observe these sub-communities among our GenCS students and see that exactly these communities are valuable for deepening knowledge and learning.

To allow our students to *access mathematical knowledge efficiently* in the online materials mentioned above, we explicate their *knowledge structure* and the *mathematical practices* and use these to support the students in interacting with the course materials.

For determining the knowledge structure we make use of the fact that mathematical knowledge is *abstract, highly structured, and extraordinary interlinked*. This allows us to more easily capture, model, relate, and represent *mathematical learning objects*. For the practices we use that mathematical communities often *interact via their mathematical knowledge artifacts*, such as theories or learning objects. We claim that their practices are *inscribed* into these artifacts. For example, mathematical authors *choose notations, make assumptions*, build on *different foundations* as well as results, and *choose typical examples* to illustrate their mathematical concepts [12].

Concretely we show in this paper, how to use our Open Mathematical Documents (OMDOC [14]) to represent mathematical learning objects as well as practices of mathematical communities. We illustrate which aspects of mathematical practices OMDOC supports and outline an extension of the format to further practices. We have implemented a collection of enabling technologies, which allow applications to interpret and manage OMDOC and its practice rep-

representations. Our enabling technologies are integrated into our prototype eLearning platform [24] to demonstrate how systems can improve the accessibility of mathematical eLearning materials.

2 Knowledge Representation for Mathematics

Mathematical Objects are what we talk and write about when we do mathematics: Rather simple objects like numbers, functions, triangles, matrices, and more complex ones such as vector spaces and infinite series. In order to provide automated services such as search or computation, we need to represent these objects in a machine-processable format, such as MATHML [32] or OPENMATH [27]. The former is a W3C recommendation for high-quality presentation of mathematical formulae on the Web, whereas the latter concentrates on the meaning of objects¹.

OPENMATH Representation	MATHML Representation	Presentation
<pre> <om:OMOBJ> <om:OMA> <om:OMS cd="combinat1" name="binomial" /> <om:OMV name="n" /> <om:OMV name="k" /> </om:OMA> </om:OMOBJ> </pre>	<pre> <m:mrow> <m:mo></m:mo> <m:mfrac linethickness="0"> <m:mi>n</m:mi> <m:mi>k</m:mi> </m:mfrac> <m:mo></m:mo> </m:mrow> </pre>	$\binom{n}{k}$

Fig. 1. OPENMATH and MATHML representation of the binomial coefficient.

Figure 1 provides the OPENMATH and MATHML representations of the number $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ of k -element subsets of a n -element set. The OMS element represents the “binomial coefficient” function, which (via `cd` and `name` attributes) points to a definition in a **content dictionary** (CD) [26]. CDs specify *commonly agreed* definitions of basic mathematical objects and allow machines to distinguish the meaning of included mathematical objects. Consequently, OPENMATH expressions can be used by information retrieval or computation services while the MATHML expression is used for display. A MATHML-aware browser presents the middle expression in Figure 1 as $\binom{n}{k}$.

The OMDoc format serves as *semantics-oriented representation format* and *ontology language* for *mathematical knowledge*. The format extends OPENMATH and MATHML with markup primitives for the structure and interrelations of mathematical objects expressed as **mathematical statements**, i.e. definitions, theorems, and proofs. We have already seen above that content dictionaries serve as an explicitly represented context for mathematical symbols, formulae and thus learning objects. The OMDoc format allows to represent CDs as OMDoc documents containing mathematical statements, but extends this functionality with a very expressive infrastructure for inter-CD relations that facilitate concept

¹ In fact MATHML has a sub-language that is equivalent to OPENMATH, but we concentrate on the presentational functionality of MATHML for simplicity.

inheritance, parametric reuse, and multiple views on mathematical content. We claim that this **theory level** makes OMDOC an ideal representation format for **mathematical learning objects** (MLO), i.e. reusable, granular, highly structured, and semantically marked up fragments of varying size.

The OMDOC approach negates the intuition of existing eLearning approaches [4, 5, 18] that learning objects (LO) should be context independent. We believe that this aim is not only impossible to achieve, but also misleading. Authors are biased when creating LOs and always include subjective, context-dependent parts influenced by their didactic approaches or personal views. In mathematics, LOs also include the authors’ individual and context-dependent practices such as their proving strategy, the choice of notations, or choice of typical examples. We believe that the context and practices of LOs should be represented explicitly so that machines can adapt them to the reader or learning goal. We call LOs with explicitly represented context-dependencies and practices “context-aware” to contrast them to the elusive “context-independent” ones. Thus, context-aware LOs allow to produce more accessible learning materials that are targeted to the individual needs and preference of the learner. For example, references to regional events or cultural aspects can motivate learners and allow them to more easily map new knowledge to prior experiences.

OMDOC allows to represent context-aware MLOs since it preserves the *logical*, *narrative*, and *social* contexts of MLOs and provides an infrastructure that interprets contextual information allowing for sophisticated semantic services [13]. For example, OMDOC supports a user-specific and context-aware selection and sequencing of LOs as well as their adaptive presentation that other non-semantic eLearning approaches can not offer [22].

3 Representing Practices in OMDoc

In the following, we detail how some of the practices above can be encoded in the OMDOC format. In this sense our paper can be seen as an instantiation of our earlier [13], where we state requirements for semantic representation formats for educational materials. We concentrate on three practices on different levels of the OMDOC format. The presentation of mathematical results (document level), the structuring and contextualisation of mathematical knowledge (theory level), and the choice of mathematical notations (object level). The approach exemplified with these examples can be applied to any practice. We analyse the mathematical objects affected by the practice and try to represent a functional core that is independent of the practice. Then we try to reify — i.e. turn into represented objects — the other factors or parameters in the practice in question. For instance for notation practices, the functional core is specified in form of the OPENMATH and MATHML formats, which define the representation of mathematical formulae. The practice factors are reified by representing the *choice of notation* for a semantic concepts and the *parameters* that can guide this choice as processable objects, see Section 3.2.

3.1 Representing Mathematical Documents

On the document level, OMDoc separates the narrative structure of mathematical documents from the content structure and thus makes it adaptable. The figure to the right² presents a technical report marked up using OMDoc’s document ontology, which defines *narrative concepts*, such as section or document, content concepts, such example or definition, and their *interrelation*, e.g an example *illustrates* a definition and a document *is a composition of* sections. The narrative relations allow us to model the *didactic practice* of authors, i.e. their way of sequencing mathematical content. The content relations are the basis for automatic generations of these sequences. For example, we can compute a guided tour that summarises all mathematical preliminaries for a given concept (see [22] for details on the automatic selection and sequencing of documents).

3.2 Representing Notation Practices in OMDoc

```

<omdoc xmlns="http://omdoc.org/ns" ...>
  <notation>see Figure 3</notation>
  <theory xml:id="MyTheory">
    <imports from="http://omdoc.org/combinat1.omdoc#binomial"/>
    <omtext xml:id="id2">
      <CMP>
        The binomial coefficients is the number of ways of choosing m objects from a
        collection of n distinct objects without regard to the order.
        We denote it by see Figure 1
      </CMP>
    </omtext>
  </theory>
</omdoc>

```

Fig. 2. OMDoc representation of an example document.

Figure 2 provides an example of a document represented in OMDoc. The OMDoc representation includes a **theory** element, which embeds a mathematical object represented in OPENMATH. The **import** element specifies the required prior mathematical knowledge and is used analogously to operators in programming languages, which import required libraries and classes. In OMDoc, the **import** elements include all symbols from other theories that are used within the current theory, but have been defined and introduced in the imported theories. In the example, the **import** element of the theory **MyTheory** includes the symbol **binomial**, which is defined in the theory **combinat1**. Please note that

² The figure was borrowed from [25]

mathematical objects in OPENMATH format can not be presented as OPENMATH represents the meaning, but can not be used for display. These objects have to be converted to MATHML. Consequently, we need to automatically process the author's notation practices, i.e. we need a mapping from OPENMATH to a respective MATHML representation.

In [15] we presented the extension of OMDOC towards the representation of mathematical notation practices to provide a flexible and context-aware conversion from OPENMATH to MATHML. We reified *notation preferences* of scientists into artifacts, that is *notation specifications*, which are applied onto the meaning of mathematical objects (represented in OPENMATH) to generate their presentation (represented in MATHML).

Figure 3 presents the OMDOC representation of a notation specification. The **prototype** pattern matches the OPENMATH expression of the binomial coefficient in Figure 2. The **rendering** elements are applied to generate a concrete presentation for the symbol. The **context** attribute of the **rendering** element associates specific context parameters. In the example, the nationality of the respective notations are added. This allows to distinguish the German, Russian, and French notation of the binomial coefficient. Analogously, further context parameters such as the expertise level (novice, intermediate, expert) or area of application (mathematics, physics) can be added.

```

<notation xmlns:m="http://www.w3.org/1998/Math/MathML"
  xmlns:om="http://www.openmath.org/OpenMath" >
  <prototype>
    <om:OMA>
      <om:OMS cd="combinat1"
        name="binomial" />
      <expr name="arg1" />
      <expr name="arg2" />
    </om:OMA>
  </prototype>
  <rendering context="language:Russian,ru">
    <m:msubsup>
      <m:mi>C</m:mi>
      <render name="arg1" />
      <render name="arg2" />
    </m:msubsup>
  </rendering>
  <rendering context="language:German,de">
    <m:mrow>
      <m:mo></m:mo>
      <m:mfrac linethickness="0">
        <render name="arg1" />
        <render name="arg2" />
      </m:mfrac>
    </m:mrow>
  </rendering>
  <rendering context="language:French,fr">
    <m:msubsup>
      <m:mi>C</m:mi>
      <render name="arg2" />
      <render name="arg1" />
    </m:msubsup>
  </rendering>
</notation>

```

Fig. 3. An Example of a notation practice represented in OMDOC.

In order to select the appropriate presentation for a symbol, we proposed a context-aware conversion algorithm in [15]. First we collect all notation specification for a mathematical object, then we collect the user's context parameters for the conversion, and finally we select an appropriate **rendering** element which best fits to the current context and apply it to generate a presentation for the mathematical object. To provide a flexible and context-aware conversion algorithm, we provide various options to collect notation specifications as well as concrete context parameters.

Given the notation specification in Figure 3 and a concrete context parameter, the mathematical object in the OMDOC document in Figure 2 can be presented differently. For example, depending on the nationality selected by the user, the binomial coefficient is presented with its German $\binom{n}{k}$, Russian C_k^n , or French notation C_n^k .

3.3 Representing Structure and Context of Math. Knowledge

To structure collections of learning objects and provide them with context OMDOC groups them into **theories** and links them via **theory morphisms**. This mechanism reifies a practice that long been relatively overt in mathematical documents, e.g. the Bourbaki development of mathematics that starts with set theory [3] and takes the mathematical practice of stating results with minimal preconditions to the extreme. OMDOC provides concrete markup for theory objects and extends the theoretically motivated accounts of inheritance and modularity in programming languages and mathematics to cover informal (but rigorous) mathematical practice (see [29] for the most recent theory, which will be incorporated into the upcoming version of OMDOC). Intuitively, a theory morphism is a mapping between theories that allows to “view” the source theory in terms of the target theory, if the mapping conserves truth. In the simplest case, theory morphisms model inheritance — the source theory can be viewed as an included part of the target theory — and thus allow to model the mathematical practice of modular/object-oriented development of knowledge in mathematics. For instance Figure 4 shows the inheritance graph of our GenCS course, and is used by students and the instructor for navigation and overview.

Fig. 4. The inheritance Graph of the GenCS course

But theory morphisms can also be used to model intra-mathematical differences in practices, e.g. differing choices of basic concepts. To gain and intuition, let consider an elementary example, the choice measuring temperature with the Kelvin, Celsius, and Fahrenheit scales. This example is suitable, since these scales make different defining assumptions — we model these as OMDOC axiom elements. For instance the Fahrenheit scale *defines* zero degrees to be the temperature of the coldest winter night Mr. Daniel Gabriel Fahrenheit ever experienced whereas the Celsius scale puts zero degrees at the freezing point of water, while the Kelvin scale puts it at the at hypothetical point, where all atoms cease motion (cf. Figure 5). The crucial observation is that (after suitable rescaling)

all arrive at compatible consequences — which we model as OMDOC theorems. This allows us to establish the rescaling mappings as theory morphisms, since they are truth-preserving.

Theory	Temp. in Kelvin	Temp. in Celsius	Temp. in Fahrenheit
Signature	$^{\circ}K$	$^{\circ}C$	$^{\circ}F$
Axiom:	absolute zero at $0^{\circ}K$	Water freezes at $0^{\circ}C$	cold winter night: $0^{\circ}F$
Axiom:	$\delta(1^{\circ}K) = \delta(1^{\circ}C)$	Water boils at $100^{\circ}C$	domestic pig: $100^{\circ}F$
Theorem:	Water freezes at $271.3^{\circ}K$	domestic pig: $38^{\circ}C$	Water boils at $170^{\circ}C$
Theorem:	cold winter night: $240^{\circ}F$	absolute zero: $-271.3^{\circ}C$	abs. zero: $-460^{\circ}F$
Theory morphisms:	$^{\circ}C \xrightarrow{+271.3^{\circ}} K$,	$^{\circ}C \xrightarrow{-32/2^{\circ}} F$,	and $^{\circ}F \xrightarrow{+240/2^{\circ}} F$

Fig. 5. Three equivalent theories of temperatures

The important implication for eLearning is that the elaborate theory structure that was theoretically motivated originally can be utilised for adaptation and bridging of context differences. We can automatically re-contextualise learning objects. For instance we can move a LO from a Fahrenheit context to a Celsius context by translating it via the appropriate mapping above. This translation is safe, since we have established it to be a theory morphism earlier. Note that the re-contextualisation discussed here significantly surpasses the notation adaption discussed above as it is at the conceptual and content level. Another example of a service based on theory morphisms is to index *all* translations and thus make the virtual cloud of possible translations available to a formula search engine like our MATHWEBSEARCH service [16]. Our experiments show that even for an introductory course like GenCS supports about three dozen non-trivial theory views, while the theory views from subsequent course into GenCS go in the hundreds, since these courses are given by other instructors.

4 Implementation & Case Study

We propose an interactive environment, henceforth referred to as *active document environment* [21], which supports personalised interaction with mathematical content by adapting documents according to the user’s practices and preferences. The figure to the right presents the constituents of active mathematical documents. The horizontal layers denote the preliminaries for the services in the vertical columns.

Machine processable representation	Configuration	Automatic Adaptation
		User modeling
	Rules	
Document Markup & Ontologies		

Document markup and ontologies provide a machine-processable representation of documents and allow us to distinguish the content, structure, and form of documents. In order to implement configurable documents, we extend the semantic representation layer with practice reifications, such as rules that express

an authors choice of content, his way of sequencing content, or preferred presentation. For example, notation definitions are rules that define the rendering of mathematical concepts depending on the author’s context. In order to provide automatic adaptation of documents, we need to model the user’s behaviour, e.g. by applying user modeling techniques. For example, in [23] we extended our configuration of mathematical notation towards an adaptive framework that applies user modeling techniques to automatically adapt notations for the user.

To demonstrate our approach, we are implementing a proof-of-concept eLearning platform [24]. The implementation of the system is ongoing. In the following, we describe our envisioned prototype.

The system integrates the Java library JOMDOC [10] to convert lecture material in OMDOC+OPENMATH into XHTML+MATHML. During the import of OMDOC materials, the lecturer can specify his notation preferences. In the figure below, the German notation has been chosen. By integrating JOBAD [7] we can allow users to adapt the presented material on-the-fly, i.e. users can change notations and indicate their preferences while reading the material.

However, dynamic adaptation of material is not always in the intention of the lecturer, as he might wish to introduce specific notations and allow students to learn new ones. Consequently, systems should not simply overwrite the lecturer’s notations, but rather add a hint for the user if his notation background differs with the presented symbols; see Figure 6 for two variants of the material above.

Fig. 6. User-specific Adaptation of Notations

5 Related Work

The ACTIVEMATH system [19] integrates a framework for automatic course generation [30] based on hierarchical network planning, which produces personalised courses that adapt to the user’s learning goals and competencies. Course are generated for different scenarios, such as the introduction of a learner to a previously unknown concept, the discovery of concepts, or the rehearsal of materials.

Content is represented in OMDOC, but the ACTIVEMATH approach does not consider the full power of the format. Instead, the course generation is based on the annotation of didactic relations and properties. Practice-oriented adaptations along mathematical sound relations are not yet supported. However, the ACTIVEMATH system offers a sophisticated user modeling approach [20], which implements the third service layer of active documents, i.e. the system-driven adaptation of documents.

The educational knowledge repository CONNEXIONS [2] is based on a corpus of semantic artifacts represented in CNXML [9], a *lightweight* XML markup language for educational content. CNXML *embeds* MATHML as well as OPENMATH for the representation of mathematical objects. It provides markup for the document level, but lacks markup of theories and theory dependencies. However, CONNEXIONS provides “lenses” [11] that allow users to express their approval or rejection. These lenses are used to select appropriate content for a user according to his membership to a specific mathematical community.

[8] specifies strategies for interactive exercises. Strategies are procedures or procedural skills that help solving exercises and thus reflect mathematical practices, similar to the problem solving guidelines presented by Polyá [28]. Based on strategy specifications, [8] implement a web service, which is used by several mathematical eLearning applications allowing them to consider alternative strategies to provide more adaptive feedback and guidance.

The MathDox system [6] presents mathematical course material in form of interactive mathematical web pages. It integrates the MathDox Player and the previously mentioned exercise service [8] to implement accessible and living eLearning documents. However, although its XML-based document format embeds mathematical objects in OPENMATH and MATHML and provides a basic markup of the structure of documents, it is less suited for representing mathematical structures and practices as it is lacking OMDOC’s theoretic foundations.

6 Conclusion & Outlook

In this paper we discussed how a modern, content-oriented document format (OMDOC) can be used to represent *context-aware* mathematical learning objects as well as practices of mathematical communities. We have shown how the context awareness of MLO representations together reified practices can be used to re-contextualise MLOs and adapt them to differing cultural backgrounds. The implementation of our prototype is work-in-progress and will be used to demonstrate how systems can improve the accessibility of eLearning materials.

Future work will address the reification of further practices in OMDOC, e.g. to support the automatic selection of typical examples and exercises for a given set of theories and user-specific context parameters. Moreover, we want to extend OMDOC to represent the social context of mathematical knowledge, i.e. information and relations that are captured during the user’s interaction with mathematical knowledge such as tags, annotations, or discussions.

References

1. AAS. Need assessment report by the academic affairs committee of the undergraduate student government, 2008. private communication.
2. R.G. Baraniuk, C.S. Burrus, B.M. Hendricks, G.L. Henry, A.O. Hero III, D.H. Johnson, D.L. Jones, J. Kusuma, R.D. Nowak, J.E. Odegard, L.C. Potter, K. Ramchandran, R.J. Reedstrom, P. Schniter, I.W. Selesnick, D.B. Williams, and W.L. Wilson. Connexions: DSP education for a networked world. In *Proceedings of the Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing., ICASSP 4*, 4144–4147. IEEE, 2002.
3. N. Bourbaki. *Theory of Sets*. Elements of Mathematics. Springer Verlag, 1968.
4. IEEE Learning Technology Standards Committee. Ieee standard for learning technology – data model for content to learning management system communication. <http://www.ieeeltsc.org/standards/1484-11-1-2004/>, 2005. seen May 2009.
5. IMS Global Learning Consortium. Learning resource metadata specification 2001. <http://www.imsglobal.org/metadata>, seen May 2009.
6. H. Cuypers, A. M. Cohen, J. W. Knopper, R. Verrijzer, and M. Spanbroek. MathDox, a system for interactive Mathematics. In J. Luca and E. R. Weippl, editors, *Proceedings of World Conference on Educational Multimedia, Hypermedia, and Telecommunications*, 5177–5182. AACE, 2008.
7. J. Giceva, C. Lange, and F. Rabe. Integrating web services into active mathematical documents. in press for Proceedings of the Conference on Intelligent Computer Mathematics.
8. B. Heeren, J. Jeuring, A. van Leeuwen, and A. Gerdes. Specifying Strategies for Exercises. In S. Autexier et al., editors, *Proceedings of the Conference on Intelligent Computer Mathematics, LNAI 5144*, 430–445. Springer Verlag, 2008.
9. B. Hendricks and A. Galvan. The Connexions Markup Language (CNXML). <http://cnx.org/aboutus/technology/cnxml/>, seen May 2009.
10. JOMDoc — a Java Library for OMDoc documents. <http://jomdoc.omdoc.org>, seen May 2009.
11. Christopher M. Kelty, C. Sidney Burrus, and Richard G. Baraniuk. Peer review anew: Three principles and a case study in postpublication quality assurance. *Special Issue on Educational Technology*, 96(6):1000–1011, 2008.
12. A. Kohlhase and M. Kohlhase. Communities of Practice in MKM: An Extensional Model. In J. Borwein and W. M. Farmer, editors, *Proceedings of the Conference on Mathematical Knowledge Management, LNAI 4108*, 179–193. Springer Verlag, 2006.
13. A. Kohlhase and M. Kohlhase. Semantic knowledge management for education. *Proceedings of the IEEE; Special Issue on Educational Technology*, 96(6):970–989, June 2008.
14. M. Kohlhase. OMDoc – *An open markup format for mathematical documents [Version 1.2]*. LNAI 4180. Springer Verlag, 2006.
15. M. Kohlhase, Christine Müller, and Florian Rabe. Notations for living mathematical documents. In S. Autexier et al., editors, *Proceedings of the Conference on Intelligent Computer Mathematics, LNAI 5144*, 504–519. Springer Verlag, 2008.
16. M. Kohlhase and I. Şucan. A search engine for mathematical formulae. In T. Ida et al., editors, *Proceedings of Artificial Intelligence and Symbolic Computation, AISC’2006, LNAI 4120*, 241–253. Springer Verlag, 2006.
17. J. Lave and E. Wenger. *Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation*. Cambridge University Press, 1991.

18. Advanced Distributed Learning. Scorm: Sharable content object reference model. <http://www.adlnet.gov/>, 2000. seen May 2009.
19. E. Melis and J. Siekmann. Activemath: An intelligent tutoring system for mathematics. In L. Rutkowski et al., editors, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing, LNAI 3070*, 91–101. Springer-Verlag, 2004.
20. E. Melis. User model description. DFKI Report, DFKI, 2001.
21. C. Müller. Active documents: personalised interactions with mathematical documents. submitted, 2009.
22. C. Müller. Specification and generation of variant documents. submitted, 2009.
23. C. Müller and M. Kohlhase. Context Aware Adaptation: A Case Study on Mathematical Notations.
24. C. Müller and M. Kohlhase. panta rhei. In A. Hinneburg, editor, *LWA Conference Proceedings*, 318–323. Martin-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg, 2007.
25. N. Müller. An Ontology-Driven Management of Change. In A. Hanft, editor, *LWA Conference Proceedings*, 186–193. Universität Hildesheim, 2006.
26. OPENMATH content dictionaries. <http://www.openmath.org/cd/>, seen May 2009.
27. OPENMATH Home. <http://www.openmath.org/>, seen May 2009.
28. G. Pólya. *How to Solve it*. Princeton University Press, 1973.
29. F. Rabe. *Representing Logics and Logic Translations*. PhD thesis, Jacobs University Bremen, 2008.
30. C. Ullrich. *Pedagogically Founded Courseware Generation for Web-Based Learning, LNCS 5260*. Springer Verlag, 2008.
31. Jacobs University. Jacobs student body statistics, 2008. private communication.
32. W3C. Mathematical Markup Language Version 3.0. <http://www.w3.org/TR/MathML3/>, seen May 2009.

7 George Goguadze The MathBridge Project

In most European countries there is a high demand for tailored remedial teaching materials for mathematics enabling the transition of students from schools to higher education, in particular engineering students. As a rule, existing content for remedial mathematics is available in a single language only, rarely online and badly accessible. Moreover, it is represented in multiple formats, in various notations, and cannot be tailored to the learners' needs.

EU Project Math-Bridge aims at changing this situation to the better and helps to bridge the gap between schools and higher education in Europe. It will provide multi-lingual and multi-cultural semantic access (e.g. search and course generation) to remedial mathematics content which adapts to the requirements of a learner and his/her subject of study. It will bring together content from different European sources and offer it in a unified way. This access will be provided through a sustainable Pan-European learning service for remedial mathematics, which will be built by collecting appropriate learning resources, extending them in terms of structure and multi-linguality and making them useful and easy-to-find. The extended formats of the content will make a wider use of standards and, hence, will make this content re-usable and between different learning environments. In order to achieve its goals Math-Bridge will study the (target) competencies required for target subjects of study, adapt existing semantic and multi-lingual search software, tailor assessment tools and methodologies, and adjust the cutting-edge ActiveMath learning environment to the remedy-scenario which includes specific diagnostic means and decisions for the transition from school to higher education. The service will be able to adapt to the level of learner competences and interests.

Moreover, Math-Bridge will enable collaborative authoring of the content on the basis of Creative Commons licenses and improve instrumental support to collaborative authoring. This will stimulate collaborative production and assembly of educational content, which, we believe, is a future must. The results will be usable way beyond mathematics.

MathBridge Project

George Gogvadze
University of Saarland

activemath

Tuesday, September 1, 2009

1

Some Facts

- entering university, learners know different things
- lots of first year course are cruel sieves
- bridging courses offered to help
- but huge adaptation hassle!

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2

Available

- intelligent personalization tools can help!
- existing content used in bridging courses is available
- adaptation techniques
 - conversion from latex via latexml to OMDoc
 - special (sometimes semi-automatic) handling for producing **OpenMath**
 - conversion to **OMDoc** from word and html
 - manual annotation
 - automatic slicing
 - special handling for producing **OpenMath**
- expert pedagogicians add metadata

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3

Tasks

- content-planning and selection
- ontology of target competencies
- content-conversion
 - semi-automated
 - quality checking (gap detection)
- interoperability extensions

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4

Bridging courses deployment

- DFKI GmbH (Coordinator)
- University of Saarland (technol. support)
- Université Montpellier 2 (French)
- University of Kassel (German)
- University of Paderborn (German)
- University of Vienna (German)
- Technological University of Tampere (Finnish)
- Open University of the Netherlands (Dutch)
- Eötvös Loránd University Budapest (Hungarian)
- Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (Spanish)
- Eurotype OHG -media asset management (dissem.)

Existing Content

- coverage for the remedial needs in the transition from school to higher education (mainly engineering)
- quality of content documented through usage in reality and feedback given by users
- license that makes reuse in Math-Bridge easy
- richness wrt. metadata, slices and mathematics representation in the existing material

Content & Tools used

Provider	Type	Quantity & Definition	Format & Quality	IPR	Current Use	Existing Metadata	Language	Additional comments
DFKI	static texts and pictures interactive exercises: Fractions	700 items	OMDoc, OpenMath, CorelDraw, Applets	CC attribution Open for all ActiveMath	School students, 50	DC, IMS MathQTI	German	
TUT	- Basic skill test -Remedial mathematics numbers, maths expressions, powers and roots, exponential and logarithmic functions, equalities, inequalities, trigonometry, derivative, integral, limits	80 exercise (exc) templates 200 pages	STACK, Apache, MySQL, Maxima, LaTeX	Open source license	TUT- first year university: up to 200, test 900	Linking to theory	Finnish	Widely tested
OUNL	Text and exercises: Calculus Discrete maths Linear algebra	25 pages, 100 exc 60 exc 100 pages	PDF, Word	CC-non- commercial share alike	OUNL- first year university: 200 students	none	Dutch	Calculus tested
UV	Interactive LOs+text: sets, elementary operations, equations, basic algebra, analytic geometry static text:	200 interactive LOs 100 items 200 pages with images	Java, prog, html, Geogebra Htm+javascript	CC attribution- non-commercial	Students between school and HE teachers	none	German	Well tested

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Content & Tools used

USAAR	Static text+ interactive exc. Calculus without integrals	1000 items	OMDoc, OpenMath, prog, Applets	Open for all ActiveMath, CC attribution	University first year. 50 students	DC, IMS MathQTI	German, English, Spanish	
Kassel	Static texts + interactive exercises + interactive LOs Arithmetic Functions Calculus Trigonometry	700 pages	XHTML, GeoGebra GeoNext JavaScript, Java, MathML, Flash	CC attribution- non-commercial	700 students in bridging courses, university first year	None	German	thoroughly tested

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Standards used

Standard	Work package	Use in project
QTI	WP2	Source format
Math-QTI	WP2, WP6	Target knowledge representation
SCORM	WP6	Reporting API
OpenMath	WP2, WP4, WP5	(target) maths format
MathML	WP2, WP4	Source format, presentation, target presentation format
OMDoc	WP2, WP7	Source format, target content format
LOM	WP2	Source format
HTML, XHTML	WP2	Source format provided cont.
OOXML/ODF	WP2	Intermediate format
OWL	WP1, WP4, WP7	Ontology
HTTP, XMLRPC	WP6, WP7	Communication protocol
URL	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP8, WP10	Addressing language

Expected Content

- Relevant domains covered
 - arithmetics, calculus, discrete math, linear algebra, logic,
 - elementary functions, basic algebra, analytic geometry
- Interoperable content
 - OMDoc, OpenMath, MathQTI formats
 - Scorm Interoperability for other interactive tools
- 6 new Domain Reasoners
 - linear algebra, logic, derivatives, fractions, etc.
- LOs in 7 languages
 - English, German, French, Finnish, Hungarian, Spanish, Dutch

Bridge with us!

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8 Olga Caprotti

Three years of JEM

In this talk, I summarize the goals and achievements of the JEM, Joining Educational Mathematics, project which has reached its conclusion after a three years lifetime.

Three years of JEM

Joining Educational Mathematics

Olga Caprotti
University of Helsinki

ECP-2005-EDU-038208

Friday, August 21, 2009

JEM-Joining Educational Mathematics

ECP-2005-EDU-038208

■ eContentPlus EU programme

4-year programme (2005–08), budget of 149 million €, tackle organizational barriers and promote take up of leading-edge technical solutions to improve accessibility and usability of digital material in a multilingual environment

■ Funding: 800000 €

■ Duration: 01/08/2006 - 31/07/2009 (36 months)

Joining Educational Mathematics

Pool together the required expertise and contribute to

- content enrichment activities
- maintenance of agreed standards
- delivery of powerful, synoptic, high-quality user information and support page

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- Helsingin Yliopisto
- Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya
- Technical University of Eindhoven
- Jacobs University
- Universiteit van Amsterdam,
- AMSTEL Institute
- University of Birmingham
- FernUniversität Hagen
- Maths for More
- NAG Ltd
- ISN Oldenburg GmbH
- RWTH Aachen University
- Univ. Nacional de Educación a Distancia
- Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
- Universidade de Lisboa
- Buskerud University College
- NTNU, Trondheim University
- Chalmers University of Technology
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- European Mathematical Society
- Liguori Editore

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Major Challenges

Foster and extend the multicultural and multilingual use of semantic markup for mathematics within the European e-learning community

- Monitor the developments of learning technologies so that mathematical content can be integrated and delivered by state-of-the-art and leading systems
- Structure, coordinate and support the user and authoring community of e-learning content in mathematics.

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Setup new initiatives

■ EU-level

- Inter2Geo
- Sci-ML, TEAM-I, Malmo, Multiteach, Rome (not funded)
- MOLTO
- Establishing Web-based Mathematical Learning Systems

■ National level

- NL: SIGMA, NKBW1-2, Intelligent Feedback, MARCH-et, MOSEM2, eclasses
- ES: i-Math, e-math++, MEL, PERSONAL(ONTO), SELL, IBEMA
- FI: MoPAL
- UK: Fetlar

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Establish portal

- Internal links (1,280,690)
- Links (654)
- Members (276)
- Publications (279)
- Learning resources (76)
- Use cases (12)
- Software and Services (27)
- Aggregated feeds (21)

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Google searches

- #: The ranking of the search query.
- %: The percentage of the top 100 queries represented by each query. For example, if the top 100 queries represent 1,000 user searches, and those users searched for **cheeseburger recipe** 270 times, that query would represent 27% of the total number of searches for the top 100 queries.
- **Query:** The search terms used.
- **Position:** The highest position any page from your site ranked for that query, averaged over the last week. Since our index is dynamic, this may not be the same as the current position of your site for this query.

Impressions : Your site appeared in these searches				Clickthrough : Users clicked on your site in these searches			
#	%	Query	Position	#	%	Query	Position
1	31%	jem	12	2	9%	mathml safar	1
2	14%	norwegian.no	9	3	8%	safari.mathml	1
3	6%	formulas.matematicas	9	4	5%	jem.thematic	1
4	5%	summative.assessment	8	5	5%	drupal.mathml	1
5	3%	www.unisa.ac.za	10	9	2%	jem.mathematics	1
6	2%	spooze.duel	9	10	1%	jemportal	1
7	1%	thematic	11	12	1%	how.to.teach.limits	1
8	1%	jem.2009	7	13	1%	jem.portal	1
9	1%	mas	12	14	1%	wismat.geometry.3d	1
10	1%	lehtonen.kari	3	18	<1%	math.bloom's.taxonomy.questions	1
11	1%	summative	9	19	<1%	mathdoc.formula.editor.download	1
12	1%	formative.and.summative.assessment	6	20	<1%	matrix.multiplication	1
13	1%	socialized	6	21	<1%	mike.serpoll	1
14	1%	exponential.function	20	22	<1%	mls.html	1
15	1%	jem.wiki	3	23	<1%	multicultural.aspects	1
16	1%	formative.and.summative	7	24	<1%	sinus.function	1
17	<1%	projects.describes	8	25	<1%	trymore.equation.editor	1
18	<1%	norwegian.no	8	26	<1%	wiki.quizzes	1
19	<1%	abaath.university	8	27	<1%	a.mathematical.approach.to.ontology.authoring.and.documentation	2
20	<1%	formulas.de.matematicas	8	28	<1%	an.orthogonal.2*2.matrices	2
21	<1%	mathml.editor	7	29	<1%	javascript.math.formula.editor	2
22	<1%	maofo.ta	8	30	<1%	jem.portal.my	2
23	<1%	berna	8	31	<1%	jemportal.com.my	2
24	<1%	formative.and.summative.assessments	8	32	<1%	olga.caprotti	2
25	<1%	it.wiki	10	15	1%	lehtonen.kari	3
26	<1%	formative.summative	6				

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Statistics

In year 1 and 2, actual statistics of the portal has exceeded the performance indicators.

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JEM Community

Developers

- software descriptions
- developers wiki

Authors

- repository
- authors wiki

End-users

- case studies
- users wiki

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- Blogs
- Folksonomies
- User-generated content (news, reviews, discussions)
- RSS aggregation & feeds
- Wiki

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Peer reviews

- If you download or use a JEM resource,
 - write a comment
 - score it
 - review it
- Software and learning resources can be rated, commented reviewed.

Short comment: *

- ▶ Clarity of learning objectives
- ▶ Credits to creators
- ▶ Professional presentation
- ▶ Appropriate reference
- ▶ Appropriate use of technology
- ▶ Accuracy of content
- ▶ Adherence to stated learning objectives
- ▶ Clear identification of target learners
- ▶ Clarity of usage instructions
- ▶ Effective/engaging use of technology
- ▶ Feedback opportunity/assessment support
- ▶ Availability of case studies
- ▶ Identification of pre-requisites
- ▶ Usability in learning environment
- ▶ Ease of navigation/user interface

▼ Accessibility

Score: *

5

Score for this axis

Review: *

Blogs and news aggregation

Do you keep an academic math blog?
Does your project web page have an RSS feed?

Let us **aggregate you**, tell us about it.

JEM NETWORK NEWS

- Presentations of Symposium on "Math tutoring: tools and feedback" online
- ocd2book has just received an award
- JEM server down on Saturday
- Synergies in the Development of Mathematical Editors
- Updates on the JEM learning repository

PLANET JEM

- Five misunderstandings about case-study research
- Mathematical note taking with ASciencePad
- DSDL: initial thoughts
- OCo 3.0 Launch party in Paris
- Public Lecture by Prof. Alan Lightman

ELEARNING PLANET

- Invatamant deschis la distanta: abordare sociologica
- European e-Inclusion Awards Shortlist
- Jornadas Net.es.5
- 16th National and 5th iNet Conference: Leading system redesign
- eLearning Awards 2008: schools share good practice using ICT in lessons

TECHNOLOGY PLANET

- Gibbs sampler
- jsMath 3.5a released
- did anyone say notation needs context?
- Installer for MathDox
- Intergeo Platform (beta) started

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WIKI

AUTHORING EDUCATIONAL E-CONTENT IN MATHEMATICS

wiki

Mathematics is a fundamental discipline in science, technology, engineering, and society. Moreover, fundamental problem solving skills, acquired when learning mathematics properly, such as structuring a problem or a situation, analyzing pre-requisites and implications, go beyond doing mathematics and influence social capabilities and behavior in our increasingly technological society.

[Add new comment](#) [Read more](#) 1410 reads

E-TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATHEMATICS

wiki

This is the JEM developers' wiki that collects the contributions of developers of e-technology suited for online mathematics. Technologies that are described here range from knowledge representation formats such as mathematical markup languages, to metadata standards for learning resources and software systems that provide rich interactive experiences of mathematical concepts.

[Add new comment](#) [Read more](#) 1370 reads

USING E-CONTENT IN MATHEMATICS/SCIENCE EDUCATION

wiki

Wiki for users of technology-enhanced and online tools for mathematics. Tips and tricks by experiences users as well as case studies are welcome in this section of the JEM wiki. Instructions on how best to use software and ICT in lecturing scenarios is also in the scope.

The main contributors to these pages are the members of the JEM network however this wiki is open to anybody who wishes to contribute. Use the contact form for any requests concerning these pages.

Before you begin, there is a short guide for contributing to the JEM wikis.

[Add new comment](#) 540 reads

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CASE STUDIES

Case studies collected and reported by community members.

If you want to add a new case study, use the [template](#) and tag it properly. The wiki editor will then be able to add your case study to this wiki page.

- ▶ Case Studies in Diagnostic Assessment
- ◉ Case Studies in Learning Objects Repositories
- ◉ Teaching mathematics to distance students
- ◉ WIRIS a tool for didactical research on curriculum

< Using e-Content in Mathematics/Science Education

up

Case Studies in Diagnostic Assessment >

[Printer-friendly version](#) [Add new comment](#) 1254 reads

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Make experts' support available

Software/Service name	Filed under:	Total hits:
MathDox Formula Editor	OpenMath editor	6052
SIWM	authoring software - wiki	5799
LatexML: A LATEX to XML Converter	Text Processing	4800
WIRIS OpenMath Tools	openmath - WIRIS	4304
WebWork	Computer Aided	3960
sTeX: Semantically Enhanced TeX	Editor Text Pr	3791
DragMath	TeX/LaTeX M	3769
WIRIS CAS	Computer Algebr	3468
Staplets	Mathematica CA	3459
STACK	Computer Aided	3441
WIRIS Editor	MathML editor	3392
EMSLa-stat	Learning and te	3371
Maplets	Java Applets	3347
Locutor	Document Mana	3343
panta.rhei	assessment and	3277
WIRIS Plugin for Moodle	Editor Plugin	3086
Locutor - ontology driven management of change	change manage	3079
WIRIS Conference	Chat Mathemat	3079
eyeWIRIS	Plugin CAS	3079
MathDox Manual and Tutorial pages	Interactive Math	3079
Kreitor	XML ? RDF extr	3079
ool2dbook	Plugin for Open	3079
WIRIS Plugin for TinyMCE	tinymce equatio	3079
CC Computational Error-Correcting Codes	Scientific/Math	3079
WIT Web Intersection Theory	Mathematica	3079
JOBAO - JavaScript Library for OMDoc-based Active Documents	www library javascript hypertext documents browser	3079

Technical contact

- Christoph Lange (3)
- SebastianXambo (2)
- nmueller (2)
- sangwinc (1)
- Oddb (1)
- cmueller (1)
- hschottm (1)
- gage (1)
- Rikko (1)
- mark (1)
- more...

User support Contact

- Christoph Lange (3)
- Ramon Eixarch (2)
- SebastianXambo (2)
- cmueller (2)
- sangwinc (1)
- burkschat (1)
- Oddb (1)
- gage (1)
- Rikko (1)
- mark (1)
- more...

Make experts' support available

Members of JEM, experts in a certain technology or use case, will provide user support. JEM in exchange will recognize their expertise and competence.

- ▶ coordinate available/current user-support
- ▶ make work easier and reusable (logs, FAQs, wiki)
- ▶ ask access rights to manage your portal sections

Friday, August 21, 2009

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Friday, August 21, 2009

Mathweb MKM Interest Group OMDoc

kwarc The KWARC Research Group
knowledge-adaptation-and-reasoning-for-content

KWARC home
 Research Interest
 People
 Projects
 Guided Research
 Events
 Teaching
 Publications
 Collaborations
 Contact
 Blogs and Wikis

Scientific Communities of Practice Workshops
 Semantic Wiki Seminar
 OpenMath3-MathML3 alignment
<http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/partner/JACU>
 talks of Christine and Christoph

Knowledge Adaptation and Reasoning for Content

Friday, August 21, 2009

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Europe-wide solutions

- MapleTA seminars in Helsinki and in Barcelona: exchange of experiences on diagnostics testing
- UNED, UOC, UAberta setup common goals for Iberian distance learning universities (e.g. talk of Antonio Costa)

Friday, August 21, 2009

Adopt common formats

- OpenMath being adopted in Inter2Geo for dynamic geometry
- LOM-based, OAI-PMH-conformant repositories: JEM, PhysNet, UOC, wizmo
- Drupal modules for JEM repository

Friday, August 21, 2009

Stimulate collaborations

- math accessibility
- math education
- cognitive psychologists
- math teachers

Friday, August 21, 2009

Events

Wednesday, November 26, 2008

09:00 - 09:45 Registration
 09:45 - 10:15 Opening SIG
 10:15 - 11:00 J. Kellen, *Engaging teachers and students in innovative mathematics technology-based applications*
 Coffee break
 11:00 - 10:00 S. Marín, *Mathematics computer development in Finland - unexpected effects*
 12:00 - 12:30 M. L. Vignares, J. Cordero and M. Faura, *Using Web-Based Assignments in Secondary School Mathematics*
 12:30 - 12:45 M. Sopena, *Should we still teach how to multiply and to divide?*
 12:45 - 13:00 S. González-Vega, *Insights from teachers*
 13:00 - 14:30 Lunch & Registration
 14:30 - 15:15 V. Shute, *Can't Get it Right? Why? Why Not? Evaluating an Assessment for Learning System Called ACT*
 Coffee break
 15:15 - 16:15 S. Rocha, *ICT in the Portuguese Education: the teacher (PGM, PNM), Student, and Infocus, and the Importance of Teacher Abilities*
 16:15 - 17:00 Panel Discussion, Facilitator: António Balle, José Francisco Rodrigues, João Vilhinho, Chao-Min Sopena
 17:00 - 17:45 JEM Business Meeting

Thursday, November 27, 2008

09:00 - 10:15 S. Oliveira, *Digital resources and mathematics teachers' documents*
 Coffee break
 10:15 - 11:15 S. Santos, *Technologies in the Mathematics Classroom: Seeking through the STACK LMS system*
 11:15 - 11:45 S. Saizuelo and S. Reinhardt, *Enhancing Apollonius' Solution through the STACK LMS system*
 11:45 - 12:15 J. Saizuelo, *Revisiting Exercises on an e-Book Reader*
 12:15 - 12:45 S. Ancherbeut and S. Pissinatti, *Impact of ICT on the Teaching of Maths to Gifted/Advanced Learners*
 12:45 - 13:00 A. Peña, *Collaborative Environment of Mathematics Digital Library*
 13:00 - 14:30 Lunch
 14:30 - 15:15 J. B. Lagrange, *Developing and experimenting a Dynamic Geometry and Computer Algebra environment*
 Coffee break
 15:15 - 15:45 S. Santos, N. Sallaber and J. Mendes, *New features in "Open Mathematics"*
 15:45 - 16:15 M. Buitrago, *EMU on the Web 2.0 - A web-based learning environment in applied statistics*
 16:15 - 16:30 R. Etxepare, *WFO Quizzes, enhancing Moodle quiz system with mathematical capabilities*
 16:30 - 16:45 M. A. Huertas, T. Sanchez-Vizoso, C. Cordero, A. Pérez-Núñez, G. Morquie, J. Vilhinho, *Automatic Identification of Mathematical Formulae for Web-Based Learning Resources*
 16:45 - 17:00 M. A. Huertas, César Cordero, Miriam Pascual, Roger Orús, Lourdes Mateo, *Proct' open repository of formulae structures*
 17:00 Workshop dinner

5TH JEM WORKSHOP
 Impact of ICT on the Teaching of Mathematics and on the Mathematics Curriculum

NOV 26, 2008 INSTITUT FINLANDAIS 9:30 AM The focus of the Workshop is the Impact of Technology on the Teaching of Mathematics.

Friday, August 21, 2009

Meeting	Date	Location
1st JEM Workshop: e+Calculus	8-9-10 February, 2007	Lisbon, PT
2nd JEM Workshop: joint with OpenMath	25-26 July, 2007	Linz, A
3rd JEM Workshop	28-29 February, 2008	Barcelona, ES
4th JEM Workshop	11 September, 2008	Trondheim, NO
5th JEM Workshop	26-27 November 2008	Paris, FR
6th JEM Workshop	19 August 2009	Aachen, D
JEM Seminar: Scientific Communities of Practice 2007	30 August, 2007	Bremen, D
JEM Seminar: New and Emerging Technologies in Mathematics Education	17-18 August, 2007	Helsinki, FI
Mathematical e-content: expressing, manipulating and retrieving mathematics online	24 April, 2008	Copenhagen, DK
JEM Seminar: VodMath, Vodcasting Mathematics	23-24 May, 2008	Helsinki, FI
JEM Seminar: Scientific Communities of Practice 2008	27 June, 2008	Bremen, D
JEM Workshop at ICME11: eLearning Mathematics	9 July, 2008	Monterrey, MX
Symposium on "Math tutoring: tools and feedback"	18-19 September, 2008	Heerlen, NL
JEM School: GF for Grammars Developers	20-29 April, 2009	Online course
JEM School: STACK, a System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel	1 June, 2009	
JEM School: Automatic assessment in mathematics education	3 June, 2009	
JEM School: IBEMA Camp on MapleTA	18-19 June	Barcelona, ES

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Lesson learned

- CMS like Drupal offer sophisticated modules to setup a community portal.
- To promote best practice, tools built on widely used systems (e.g. Drupal, moodle) are more likely to be adopted sooner.
- Peer reviewing and rating of resources does not work, just as metadata entering does not. There is no reward in doing it.
- Bridges to other communities take time to build.

Join the JEM Community
<http://www.jem-thematic.net>

Thank you!

Friday, August 21, 2009

9 Christoph Lange

Towards a Wiki for Interactive Educational Mathematics

Two tools addressing different aspects of educational mathematical documents have been developed in our research group and presented to the JEM community at previous occasions: SWiM is a semantic wiki for collaborating on such documents, and JOBAD is a framework that allows for reading documents interactively. In this paper, we outline a vision of an integrated educational environment for interactive learning and collaboration. Starting from an overview of the current state of both SWiM and JOBAD, we show how the vision can be achieved by integrating both systems.

Towards a Wiki for Interactive Educational Mathematics

Christoph Lange

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Abstract. Two tools addressing different aspects of educational mathematical documents have been developed in our research group and presented to the JEM community on previous occasions: SWiM is a semantic wiki for collaborating on such documents, and JOBAD is a framework that allows for reading documents interactively. In this paper, we outline a vision of an integrated educational environment for interactive learning and collaboration. Starting from an overview of the current state of both SWiM and JOBAD, we show how the vision can be achieved by integrating both systems.

1 Vision

We envision an integrated environment that is potentially open to all aspects of mathematics in education. The system would consist of a database of educational mathematical knowledge, but also be interlinked with external resources on the web. Both learners and teachers would collaborate in that system. Learners would mainly consume educational content. That does not only mean reading static documents, as they have been prepared by the teachers, but we envision interactive documents that invite the reader to explore additional information – inside the knowledge base, or involving external resources or web services –, and to modify the presentation of the knowledge according to their preferences. Teachers would mainly contribute content to the knowledge base, or maintain existing content. But learners would also be able to contribute – their homeworks, for example. All users of the system would be connected to each other by a commenting function: Learners would be able to comment on documents provided by teachers – e. g. giving them feedback on how well they understand them. Conversely, teachers would give learners feedback on their homework. The same feature could also be used for *peer review* – both among learners and among teachers. The system would support users to point out what exactly they consider wrong or improvable in given resources, and, possibly, how they would improve the content. Based on that information, the system would be able to assist authors.

The system that we envision has the potential to blur the boundaries between readers and writers, learners and teachers. While we consider this technically feasible, we are aware of the fact that it may not always be socially desirable. Therefore, the system should have a comprehensive permission management, and we leave the decision on what collaboration features to enable to the teachers setting up the system.

2 Current State

Our current systems realise part of this vision. The SWiM semantic wiki integrates both the author’s and the reader’s role in a coherent environment. Currently, however, its functionality is targetted at people engineering semiformal mathematical knowledge, such as OpenMath Content Dictionaries [LGP08,Lan09b]. Previous development efforts focused on collaboration on mathematical knowledge rather than on improving their consumption. However, our research group has made progress on investigating mathematical documents in education from a reader’s perspective and provided the JOBAD framework (JavaScript API for QMDoc-based Active Documents), which makes mathematical documents interactive by integrating them with web services [GLR09]. This architecture can only reveal its full strength, though, when integrated with a powerful backend – which has not been done yet.

For lack of space, we omit a review of related work but refer the reader to previous publications on SWiM and JOBAD. We aim at providing a system that offers more interactive knowledge-based services than non-semantic websites like the mathematical section of Wikipedia, but at the same time is more agile than existing solutions like MathDox or ActiveMath [MGH+06,CCK+08].

2.1 SWiM, a Wiki for Mathematics

Recent development of SWiM has mainly been motivated by the requirements for maintaining the OpenMath Content Dictionaries on the OpenMath site [Lan09a,Lan09b]. We have some evidence, however, that some of the experiences made in that ongoing case study have a more general impact. Therefore, part of them may be transferable to educational settings, too.

SWiM inherited an elaborate permission management from the underlying IkeWiki system. Both in Content Dictionary maintenance and in education, there are users with different roles in the community. In education, we could distinguish:

- Pure consumers** who merely read educational contents in the system
- Commenting readers** who may give feedback on educational resources
- Teachers** who may edit educational documents and comment on documents containing foundational background knowledge, such as OpenMath Content Dictionaries, which contain formal definitions of mathematical symbols used in educational documents
- Full editors** who additionally have full access to the Content Dictionaries.

Technically, educational documents and Content Dictionaries are the same to SWiM. They merely differ in their degree of formality. To a learner, SWiM offers various interfaces to browsing documents (see [LGP08]): There can be usual inline links in the document, semantically related documents (e. g. documents imported as prerequisites for the current one, or examples for the definition currently viewed) are accessible via a navigation toolbar, and all mathematical symbols in formulae are linked to the place where they have been defined in a Content Dictionary.

Fig. 1. Part of a discussion page from the OpenMath wiki. Notice the post types and the specialised reply buttons.

Every document has a discussion page. It works like a usual discussion forum but has been extended towards domain-specific problem-solving assistance. Users can give discussion posts and replies exact *types*. We have conducted a survey in the OpenMath and JEM community¹ to elicit patterns of common problem and solution types. For example, a definition of a mathematical concept can be hard to understand, and a common solution would be to provide an example [LHC08]. Once such a standard solution pattern has been suggested, the system can assist the user with implementing it in the knowledge base.

SWiM offers dedicated editing support for all structures of mathematical knowledge (cf. [LGP08]): There is an editor for rich text, extended by a toolbar for adding structural annotations like proof steps. Metadata of documents are editable in a separate form, and finally there is a visual but nevertheless semantic formula editor. In the OpenMath case study, we have found out that SWiM is particularly suited for three use cases that are common in Content Dictionary maintenance: performing minor fixes, discussing and implementing revisions, and editing and verifying notations of mathematical symbols [Lan09b].

2.2 Interactive Documents with JOBAD

JOBAD, the JavaScript API for OMDoc-based Active Documents, is a specification of a MathML-based document format and an HTTP-based communication protocol that enables interactivity in mathematical documents [GLR09, JOB09]. The overall architecture is shown in fig. 2. As shown at the bottom, a JOBAD-enabled document is encoded in XHTML+MathML, where the MathML formulae are annotated semantically by cross-linked parallel markup (i. e. every formula

¹ The survey is still open for participation at <http://tinyurl.com/5qdetd> but likely to be replaced by a more focused survey soon.

is given in a human-readable presentation and a machine-readable structural representation). Interactive services utilise these annotations.

Fig. 2. JOBAD architecture: note the central role of the rendering service, which both generates JOBAD-compliant documents and is used by other services.

First, there are in-document services (shown in blue) that change the appearance of the document without requiring further interaction with a server – provided, the document has been prepared accordingly. A bracket elision service flexibly shows or hides brackets in mathematical formulae, aiming at making complex formulae more comprehensible. A folding service can replace complex subterms by abbreviations – either author-defined ones, such as W_{pot} for $\frac{-e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 R/2}$ in a physical formula, or default ones like “...”. Then, there are symbol-based services, where additional information about a mathematical symbol selected by the user is requested from a web service backend. We have currently implemented interactive lookup of a symbol’s definition and type from a Content Dictionary. First feedback from users shows that definition lookup is particularly useful in educational practice [Gic09]. Work on a notation selection service, which allows for customizing the appearance of individual mathematical symbols, is currently in progress (cf. [KLM⁺09]). Finally, there are service that send complex mathematical expressions to a web service, in order to have them computed, verified, or rewritten. As a proof of concept, we have implemented a connection to an OpenMath-based unit conversion web service [SD08]. Both client and server side of the latter two types of services are shown in purple in fig. 2. In our current client-side implementation, interactions can be selected from a context menu or by keyboard shortcuts (shown on the left). They either apply to the mathematical symbol the user clicked on, or to the subterm selected by the user.

As said above, JOBAD is not limited to the services that *we* have implemented, but extensible. On the client, calls to services are represented by generic action objects instead of being hard-wired into the context menu, which paves the road for alternative user interfaces. On the server, any existing mathematical web service can be integrated. The programmer only has to provide a client-side

action object that makes an appropriate request to the web service and processes the response received from the web service. The response can either be used to replace the current mathematical formula, or it can be displayed separately, e. g. in a popup window. JOBAD provides a rich set of utility functions for both.

3 Integration Roadmap

The basic integration of JOBAD with SWiM will be straightforward. For rendering documents, SWiM already relies on the JOMDoc library [JOM], which renders documents in a JOBAD-compliant format. In that stage of integration, JOBAD's lookup services would then access the Content Dictionaries from the SWiM knowledge base, thus making sure that a learner can look up exactly those mathematical definitions that have been provided by his teacher. We are planning to extend definition lookup to definition *expansion*: it will be possible to insert the definition of a symbol in place of the symbol, which theoretically works for all types of definitions except implicit ones.

Not only definition lookup can be realised with SWiM; the discussion support could be made more interactive as well. Currently, questions or problem reports about mathematical concepts can only be posted from the page of the respective concept. In a JOBAD-enhanced system, access to the discussion forums can additionally be given from the place where it is actually needed: from any mathematical formula where the user encounters a symbol that he wants to discuss. Thanks to its semantic web nature, SWiM also has the potential to link resources in its own database to external ones on the web. One can easily establish a link from a mathematical concept to, e. g. its historical background, as given on Wikipedia or Wolfram's MathWorld. By a simple enhancement, JOBAD could then provide such links to the user in his current interaction context.

Users who tried the JOBAD demo and interactive adapted mathematical documents while reading, frequently asked whether they could save their adaptations somewhere [Gic09]. As SWiM manages user accounts anyway, such an enhancement would easily be possible. Not only on explicit request, but also *during* interaction with the system, we could build user profiles – assuming the user's consent. A logging service, immediately notifying a web service about any kind of adaptation requested by the user, would help teachers and developers to find out more about how learners interact with mathematical documents and what adaptation features they consider useful. Given that a lot of mathematical web services exist that have already been successfully evaluated in educational settings, they should also be integrated with JOBAD. Examples known to the JEM community are the services originally developed for the ActiveMath [MGH⁺06] and MathDox environments [CCK⁺08], performing tasks such as interactive exercise feedback [HJvLG08]; see [GLR09] for an overview.

Finally, we aim at enabling interactive access to larger-scale mathematical structures than formulae. Based on semantically annotated HTML, we have developed an interactive visualization of rhetorical structures in mathematical documents that are rather text-oriented than formula-heavy, as is frequently the

case in educational documents [Gic08]. We want to enable the same for structured proofs, e.g. allowing for interactively folding proof steps.

Acknowledgments : The author would like to thank Jana Giceva for implementing large parts of the JOBAD framework and collecting first feedback from users. This work was supported by JEM-Thematic-Network ECP-038208.

References

- ACR⁺08. S. Autexier, J. Campbell, J. Rubio, V. Sorge, M. Suzuki, and F. Wiedijk, editors. *Intelligent Computer Mathematics, MKM*, number 5144 in LNAI. Springer, 2008.
- CCK⁺08. H. Cuypers, A. M. Cohen, J. W. Knopper, R. Verrijzer, and M. Spanbroek. MathDox, a system for interactive Mathematics. In *World Conference on Educational Multimedia, Hypermedia and Telecommunications*. AACE, 2008.
- Gic08. J. Giceva. Capturing Rhetorical Aspects in Mathematical Documents using OMDoc and SALT. Technical report, Jacobs University, DERI Galway, 2008. Available from: https://svn.kwarc.info/repos/supervision/intern/2008/giceva_jana/project/internship%20report.pdf.
- Gic09. J. Giceva. Integrating web services into active mathematical documents. Bachelor thesis, Jacobs University Bremen, 2009.
- GLR09. J. Giceva, C. Lange, and F. Rabe. Integrating web services into active mathematical documents. In J. Carette, L. Dixon, C. Sacerdoti Coen, and S. Watt, editors, *MKM/Calculus*, number 5625 in LNAI. Springer, 2009.
- HJvLG08. Bastiaan Heeren, Johan Jeuring, Arthur van Leeuwen, and Alex Gerdes. Specifying Strategies for Exercises. In Autexier et al. [ACR⁺08].
- JOB09. JOBAD framework – JavaScript API for OMDoc-based active documents, 2009. Available from: <https://jomdoc.omdoc.org/wiki/JOBAD> [cited February].
- JOM. JOMDoc Project — Java Library for OMDoc documents. Available from: <http://jomdoc.omdoc.org> [cited March 2009].
- KLM⁺09. M. Kohlhase, C. Lange, C. Müller, N. Müller, and F. Rabe. Notations for active mathematical documents. KWARC Report 2009-1, Jacobs University Bremen, 2009. Available from: http://kwarc.info/publications/papers/KLMMR_NfAD.pdf.
- Lan09a. C. Lange. OpenMath wiki [online]. 2009. Available from: <http://wiki.openmath.org> [cited February].
- Lan09b. C. Lange. wiki.openmath.org – how it works, how you can participate. In James H. Davenport, editor, *22nd OpenMath Workshop*, 2009.
- LGP08. C. Lange and A. González Palomo. Easily editing and browsing complex OpenMath markup with SWiM. In P. Libbrecht, editor, *Mathematical User Interfaces Workshop*, 2008.
- LHC08. C. Lange, T. Hastrup, and S. Corlosquet. Arguing on issues with mathematical knowledge items in a semantic wiki. In J. Baumeister and M. Atzmüller, editors, *LWA (Lernen, Wissensentdeckung und Adaptivität)*, 2008.
- MGH⁺06. E. Melis, G. Goguadze, M. Homik, P. Libbrecht, C. Ullrich, and S. Winterstein. Semantic-aware components and services of ActiveMath. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 37(3), 2006.
- SD08. J. Stratford and J. H. Davenport. Unit knowledge management. In Autexier et al. [ACR⁺08].

10 Leendert van Gastel, Hans Cuypers, Henk van der Kooij, Dirk Tempelaar, Evert van de Vrie

Use the Web to Close the Mathematics Gap

In the Netherlands, a severe gap is felt between secondary and higher education when it comes to mathematics. For several years, a dispute is raging about causes and remedies. The gap in the mathematics transition was even a central topic in a parliamentary investigation into the problematic outcomes of educational innovations. In the meantime, a country-wide initiative was deployed to close the gap, especially focusing on the shortcomings in algebraic skills (<http://www.nkbw.nl>). It brings together a broad range of mathematics materials in a web-based repository. Good practices of remedial courses are shared. Teams of teachers from secondary and higher education develop algebraic skills tests, that are positioned as a benchmark for algebraic skills. Interactive versions of the tests of publicly are available for practicing and for communicating the expectations about content and level.

Use the Web to Close the Mathematics Gap

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1 The Mathematics Problem in the Netherlands

Around 2000, in the Lisbon Agenda, the European Community has set a goal of 50% participation in higher education. The number of laureates counts, so apart from an increase in the influx, the study success is important, including the reduction of dropout rates and of study delay. Tартly enough, at this time a gap developed between secondary and higher education concerning mathematics. The success rates were under pressure. For instance, in 2004 at the chemistry department of the University of Amsterdam, the success rate of Calculus 1 dropped from 80% to 45%. In that year, the decline for the mathematics and physics departments was less pronounced, but still about 13%. Study delay increased. While in 2003 for Calculus 1 a single reexamination was sufficient, in 2006 five reexaminations were organized to give the students ample opportunity to pass.

The problem is not limited to the exact sciences, also the technical and economics disciplines suffer from the decrease in algebraic skills. Meanwhile, not only the transition from secondary to higher education deserves attention, the influx from vocational education to higher education, and also the step from professional higher education to an academic master turn out to be problematic.

Where do these problems come from? At the end of the previous century, large scale innovations have changed secondary education in the Netherlands. These educational innovations turned out to have a considerable negative side-effect on the level of algebraic skills.

Fig. 1. Success rates at first mathematics course

Study program	cohort	# of students	Success rate 1st Math Course
Groningen, sciences	2007	159	25%
Utrecht, chem	2006	83	25%
Maastricht, business	2006	1030	47%
Delft, electr	2007	354	37%
Fontys, polytechnics	2007	48	40%
Utrecht, econ	2007	262	38%

1.1 Educational Innovations

In 2007/2008 the Dutch Parliament organized an investigation into educational innovations [1]. The reason to organize the investigation was a serious concern in society about the results of education. Such a parliamentary investigation is an important political instrument in the Netherlands, for which the parliament may opt independently of the government. Members of parliament form the committee, hearings are held with responsible politicians and experts that take an oath. The main conclusion was that the Dutch government seriously neglected the main task of ensuring proper education.

In the investigation four educational innovations were addressed, here we discuss three of them in more detail: (1) the so-called "profiling" of the curriculum, the (2) the non-differentiated first three year of secondary education, the so called "basis formation" (in Dutch "basisvorming"), and (3) a pedagogic approach, called "new learning".

Up to 1999, each secondary school student from age 15 to 18 had freedom to choose subjects, within certain boundaries. To ameliorate the transition to higher education, four "profiles" were developed that consist of coherent packages of subjects that should prepare for higher education. These profiles are Culture & Society, Culture & Economy, Nature & Health and Nature & Technology. Representatives from secondary and higher education participated in the development of the profiles and the new subject contents.

The "basisvorming", literally the "basis formation", refers to the first three years of secondary education. In the old situation, children had to choose at the age of 12 the school type, which led to an early selection. To fully understand the concept, it is good to know that for decades the social-democratic party in the Netherlands promoted the idea of a "mid school" ("middenschool") to stimulate equality and to postpone the moment of selection. This idea was stuck in the political arena. However, an advice of the Scientific Council led to a political consensus in which the existing formal school structure was preserved. A distinction of two levels was proposed and concrete attainment targets were replaced by broader primary goals.

The idea of "new learning" was developed in the time frame of the nineties with an almost limitless belief in the opportunities that Internet would create. The characteristics of new learning are

- An activating learning environment with attention paid to independent learning;
- Meaningful and authentic contexts;
- Cooperation between learners;
- Different role for the teacher (less knowledge transfer, more coaching).

This innovation was different from the other innovations by the government. It was not installed by law like the others. Government started a project that in a pro-active role stimulated new learning at the same time as the introduction of the profiles.

1.2 Findings of the parliamentary investigation

The investigation committee was quite critical in their final report [1]. The effects of the "basis formation", the approach of first three years of the secondary education were found to be limited. There was no direct evidence that the moment of choosing by students was at a later age. The committee found a lack of scientific evidence of the "new learning" approach. The opinion about this semi-official innovation was that it was quite risky. In addition the base conditions like support of teachers and coaching of students were not met and the differences in content and learning style were not sufficiently taken into account. The effects of the profiling system were disturbing. The main goal was the improvement of the transition to higher education. But the number of laureates diminished because switching between the school levels became more difficult. Fewer students opted for scientific and technical disciplines, and this effect was especially noteworthy among female students.

In the analysis of these effects, the committee notes that the main reasons for changing secondary education, i.e. more equality in society and lowering dropout rates in higher education were lying outside of secondary education itself. Although it may be legitimate, there is a clear danger that the innovation will not reach its goals because of a lack of support within secondary education. Moreover, during the innovations, the responsibilities of government and the schools became confused. Government interfered with pedagogy, and quality insurance was too much left over to the schools.

1.3 The impact on mathematics education, especially algebraic skills

All three educational innovations had a negative impact on the level of algebraic skills of the students starting with higher education. The introduction of the "basis formation" led to a less pronounced learning results. Especially for the better students preparing for higher education, the mathematical fundament became weaker. The just installed committee for a new mathematics curriculum, criticized the "basis formation" in this way [2].

The new learning concept had a strong influence on the teaching practice. Typically, mathematics lessons consisted of say 30% explanation, and 70% doing exercises with the teacher assisting. With the "new learning" approach, the

number of contact hours diminished and students were expected to do more self-study. In the case of mathematics, typically exercises would be done in the self-study hours, without a mathematics teacher to support.

Regarding the choice for one of the profiles, only a small number of students chose the profile Nature & Technology. Higher education in science and technology felt threatened and started to allow also students with profile Nature & Health. So, one of the possible merits, a thorough preparation for technology disciplines, evaporated at the very beginning of this innovation. Moreover, the students and schools complained about an overburdened program. Indeed, motivated by the idea of writing for the right selection of students, the developers had broadened the scope and the depth of the curriculum in all disciplines. Unfortunately, time constraints prevented to find a balance between the disciplines that formed a profile. So this resulted in an study overload for the students.

The complaints reached the political platform soon. In 2006, an amendment was proposed by the minister that yielded less hours available for many disciplines, among which mathematics. Now many scientists and teachers complained about these proposed measures. Even larger impact had a student movement called "Lieve Maria" (Dear Maria). This name refers to the opening of a letter of a made-up student to the Dutch minister of Education, Maria van der Hoeven. In this letter [3], students mention the problems that they encounter with algebraic skills when arriving at the university. As a result, algebraic skills were on the political agenda. For mathematics the reduction of hours was somewhat diminished. Moreover, a Resonance group with established mathematics lecturers in higher education as members was installed by the Dutch Ministry of Education to follow closely the plans of the new curriculum committee for mathematics in the secondary school, especially with regard to algebraic skills.

The resonance group recommended three aspects [4]. (1) A continuous development of mathematics ability needs to be reestablished through all levels of the mathematics education. Mathematics education has become fragmented. A continuous line of development of mathematical ability is missing. (2) Reconsideration of the role of the context in the mathematics education. Since two decades, following the ideas of Hans Freudenthal, mathematics education was reformed by introducing contexts for all topics. These contexts helped to motivate students and to connect mathematics to its surroundings. However, the resonance group pointed out that in higher education the context to do mathematics was the discipline itself, like economics, and not a per exercise constructed situation. Moreover, abstract mathematics was missing to a large extent. (3) Reduction of the use of tools, in mathematics teaching and during the final central examination. Another mathematics education innovation of the nineties that the resonance group mentioned, is the introduction of the graphical calculator. In the spirit of bringing more ICT to the classroom, the graphical calculator replaced the standard calculator and brought quite some functionality to the student, such as graphing and tabulating functions, finding zeroes, etc. In practice, the students used this tool to a much higher extent than expected. Both the strong

focus on contexts and the use of the graphical calculator bore a negative impact on the level of algebraic skills.

In summary, we see that Dutch mathematics education faced five educational innovations, three generic innovations and two specific for mathematics education. All these innovations had specific goals that were met in most cases, but had a negative overall effect on algebraic skills. It is hard to discern which effect is due to which innovation, as the effects were all in the same time frame.

Also the Dutch Council of Education (Onderwijsraad), has looked into the matters of transition from secondary to higher education [6]. They find that especially the disciplines of Dutch, English and Mathematics suffer from problems. Their report contains the advice to let secondary and higher education together develop arrangements about the entrance level. This arrangement should yield a series of tests that students may access via Internet to check their level.

After the recommendations of the resonance group, the debate went on. In particular, in a petition *Stop Deforestation Mathematics Education* [5], it was pointed out that the balance was now too much in favor of the algebraic skills, which would damage the image of mathematics and also the transition to higher education. Finally, the Ministry of Education reached agreement with the new mathematics curriculum committee for mathematics about a clear presence of the development of algebraic skills. However, after acceptance of the new curriculum it will take six more years before students will enter higher education that have followed this curriculum.

2 A country-wide initiative

In the Netherlands, the SURF Foundation represents the higher educational institutions regarding ICT matters. In particular, it coordinates the distribution of government funding of ICT related projects in higher education. In 2006, in view of the Lisbon agenda, SURF started a National Action Program E-learning to stimulate projects that contribute to the goal of 50% participation in higher education.

Thirteen higher educational institutions that were struggling with the mathematics skills of the new students, were gathered in a special interest group SIGMA (www.sigma.nl). From there, they started a project "Nationale Kennisbank Basisvaardigheden Wiskunde (National Knowledge Bank Basic Skills Mathematics) in this framework of SURF to share experiences and materials. The first projects were allowed only a limited life time of one year, but a successor project NKBW2 was started in 2008 that runs into 2010. The consortium was reinforced with participants from secondary education.

The idea was to meet the gap between secondary and higher education with

- Remedial education to bridge the gap for the student;
- Activities to close the gap.

2.1 Repository

Remedial education is characterized by a large heterogeneity among the new students. It would certainly benefit from a small teacher to student ratio, but typically there is no structural money to cope with transitional problems. Therefore, the use of ICT can worthwhile since it gives students 24h access to the materials, and possibilities for customization, for automatic feedback. Especially for mathematics, possibilities arise such as generating tests, programming feedback, adaptive tests, etc. A good solution is to be found in the development of a repository for learning materials for algebraic skills. In the project NKBW a start has been made with the repository Wizmo (www.wizmo.nl) that brings together many of the materials for the previous projects. It offers open access to teachers on the basis of the creative commons license. To every learning object, metadata are attached according to the LOM-standard and an extension of the Living Math taxonomy.

Among other objects, Wizmo contains learning objects from

- the MathMatch-project containing Maple TA question banks for algebraic skills;
- the Digital Mathematics Environment, developed by the Freudenthal Institute of Utrecht University;
- The project Wortel TU/e of the Technical University of Eindhoven;
- A selection of FAQ-questions from the site WisFaq, developed by Willem van Ravenstein.

2.2 Algebraic skills tests as benchmark

To help to close the gap, it is important that at this moment there is a distinction between what secondary education sees as a reasonable endpoint of the algebraic skills, and what higher education sees as a reasonable starting point. This distance becomes especially clear when the various entrance tests of higher education is compared with the recently published exit test secondary education [7]. Part of the distance can be explained by use of unknown mathematical language or by uncommon use of variables, but there remains a difference in contents and complexity. In the project NKBW a team of teachers from secondary and higher education develop algebraic skills tests, that are positioned as a kind of calibration point for the transition. An example of such a test can be found at [9].

These algebraic skills tests are tried out at secondary education schools and at the higher education institutes to collect student results and reactions of teachers at both sides of the transition. By means of the repository, interactive versions of the tests are made publicly available for practicing and for communicating the expectations about content and level. Once well-balanced tests are found, these are put forward to gain support from organizations like the association of mathematics teachers, the Dutch mathematics society, the mathematics examination committee, the committee for the new mathematics curriculum, etc.

These tests are not a replacement of the final examination for mathematics of secondary education. The tests are developed from the perspective of transition, so for instance "mathematics A" to economics, and "mathematics B" to sciences. Moreover, it concerns only a part of mathematics, i.e. the algebraic skills, for which it turned out that a fine-grained agreement is mandatory and that needs example tests to really express contents and complexity.

2.3 Transitional Remedial Education

From the participating higher education institutes, eighteen Bachelor programs participate in the NKBW project with their transitional remedial education courses. Disciplines vary from chemistry to polytechnics to economics.

The experiences in the first NKBW project indicate that investments in the transitional remedial education help to raise the study success of the first year of higher education [8]. Algebraic skills are very important for the first mathematics course. Typically, this course is important for the first year, not only because of its own credit points, but also because it supports disciplinary courses. In the project, a common goal is set to reach over two years a 10% decrease of study dropout and delay concerning the first mathematics course. So this directly influences the goals of the Lisbon agenda.

In the project,

- plans for these courses are shared and reviewed;
- materials are shared via the repository Wizmo;
- the algebraic skills tests are tried out;
- data are gathered for a baseline and effect measurement about student results and student and staff satisfaction;
- results are compared and evaluated.

The outcome will be several good practices of education for the transition in mathematics. Monitoring of the data is set-up to follow the trends and to search for effects of the various approaches. When the approach is successful, we will see a raise of the level of algebraic skills and a decline of dropout rates and study delay.

References

1. Dijsselbloem, J., e.a. (2008), Tijd voor Onderwijs, Eindrapport parlementair onderzoek onderwijs- vernieuwingen, KST113842, 's-Gravenhage: Sdu Uitgevers.
2. Siersma, D. e.a. (2007), Rijk aan Betekenis, Visie op vernieuwd wiskundeonderwijs. Commissie Toekomst Wiskundeonderwijs. <http://www.fi.uu.nl/ctwo/publicaties/>
3. Van Rest, F., Hauwert, G. (2006). Lieve Maria, public letter to Minister of Education, <http://www.lievementia.nl>.
4. Van de Craats, J. e.a. (2007), Standpunt van de Resonansgroep wiskunde ten aanzien van de wiskundevoorstellen havo en vwo voor 2007 en later, Resonansgroep wiskunde. <http://www.resonansgroepwiskunde.nl>

5. <http://www.ipetitions.com/petition/wiskunde/>
6. http://www.onderwijsraad.nl/upload/publicaties/282/documenten/een_succesvolle_start_in_het_hoger_onderwijs.pdf
7. Rozenhart, H. Instaptoetsen! Uitstaptoetsen?, Euclides 83.2, november 2007)
8. Van Gastel, L.J., Jonker, V., (Eds.). (2008). Aansluitmonitor Wiskunde VO-HO. Amsterdam: Consortium NKBW (www.nkbw.nl), ISBN 978-90-70786-07-6
9. <http://www.nkbw.nl>

11 Mika Seppälä
JEM outlook closing remarks

PERSPECTIVES IN ELEARNING

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BAD AACHEN

GOALS

Make the delivery of education more effective and more efficient.

GOALS: EFFECTIVE

effective |i'fektiv|

adjective

1 successful in producing a desired or intended result :
effective solutions to environmental problems.

GOALS: EFFECTIVE

GOALS: EFFICIENT

efficient |i'fi sh ənt|

adjective

(esp. of a system or machine) achieving maximum productivity with minimum wasted effort or expense : *fluorescent lamps are efficient at converting electricity into light.*

- (of a person) working in a well-organized and competent way : *an efficient administrator.*
- [in combination] preventing the wasteful use of a particular resource : *an energy-efficient heating system.*

EFFICIENT?

EDUCATION VS. ON-LINE EDUCATION

The US colleges and universities industry includes about 4,300 degree-granting institutions with combined annual revenue of approximately \$400 billion. (First Research Inc. 2009).

Gartner are reporting that US e-learning revenues will rise to \$622.8M this year (2008) from \$541.4 million last year.

EDUCATION VS. ON-LINE EDUCATION

● Traditional ● eLearning

WHERE IS THE SWEET SPOT?

How can technology be used to make traditional instruction more **effective** and more **efficient**?

WHAT DO WE HAVE?

- Learning Managements Systems.
- Repositories.
- Metadata.
- Intelligent Tutoring Systems.

WHAT CAN WE DO?

- Offer automatic private instruction.
- Replace books by eContent.
- Replace traditional contact instruction by virtual instruction.

EDUCATION VS. ON-LINE EDUCATION

● Traditional ● eLearning

...TARGET REMAINS.

...TARGET REMAINS.

SWEEP SPOT IN CONTACT INSTRUCTION

Assessment for Learning vs.
Assessment of Learning.

assessment |ə'sesmənt|

noun

the evaluation or estimation of the nature, quality, or ability of someone or something

ASSESSMENT FOR LEARNING

Embed assessment into instruction as an instrumental part of the learning process.

REAL TIME QUIZZES

- Embedded in normal teaching.
- Instructor explains a method or a result.
- Instructors shows examples,
- ... and asks quiz questions periodically.

PERSONAL RESPONSE SYSTEM CLICKERS

- Special devices allowing students to answer multiple choice questions.
- Uses bluetooth to connect to a computer in the class-room.
- Stores the results in the class-room computer.

ASSESSMENT FOR LEARNING

Integrating assessment in the learning process changes the dynamics of the class room.

Students are much more focused than otherwise.

The instructor gets immediate feedback and can act accordingly.

Question 1

For which values of p the integral $\int_0^1 x^p dx$ converges?

- 1 For all values of p .
- 2 Only for $p < -1$.
- 3 Only for $p > 0$.
- 4 Only for $p < 0$.
- 5 Only for $p > -1$. **Correct Answer**
- 6 For no values of p .

Question 2

For which values of p the integral $\int_1^{\infty} x^p dx$ converges?

- 1 For all values of p .
- 2 Only for $p < -1$. **Correct Answer**
- 3 Only for $p > 0$.
- 4 Only for $p < 0$.
- 5 Only for $p > -1$.
- 6 For no values of p .

Question 3

For which values of p the integral $\int_0^{\infty} x^p dx$ converges?

- 1 For all values of p .
- 2 Only for $p < -1$.
- 3 Only for $p > 0$.
- 4 Only for $p < 0$.
- 5 Only for $p > -1$.
- 6 For no values of p .

$\int_1^{\infty} x^p dx$ converges only if $p < -1$.

$\int_0^1 x^p dx$ converges only if $p > -1$.

$\int_0^{\infty} x^p dx$ only if $p < -1$ and $p > -1$.

Question 3

For which values of p the integral $\int_0^{\infty} x^p dx$ converges?

- 1 For all values of p .
- 2 Only for $p < -1$.
- 3 Only for $p > 0$.
- 4 Only for $p < 0$.
- 5 Only for $p > -1$.
- 6 For no values of p .

Correct Answer

REAL TIME QUIZZES

- Over 76% of students found quizzes useful.
- Correlation with exam results: 0.8.
- Allow the instructor to adjust his or her teaching.

Student views on Real Time Quizzes Calculus II at FSU, Spring 2009

Quizzes have been useful.

Strongly Agree	34%
Agree	42%
Neutral	16%
Disagree	8%
Strongly Disagree	0%

Student views on Real Time Quizzes Calculus II at FSU, Spring 2009

**Over 76% of students found
the Real Time Quizzes useful.**

Student views on Real Time Quizzes Calculus II at FSU, Spring 2009

... the quiz's **really helped**.
Explaining something and then
asking us a question helped me
learn ...

Anonymous comment.

FUTURE WORK

- Develop content and technology for the new assessment.
- Run large scale experiments in classrooms in Europe.
- Get from "Best Practices" to "**Next Practices**"

...TARGET REMAINS.

...TARGET REMAINS.

Commander, do you have visual? We need visual confirmation.

Has the target been destroyed?

Negative.

Target remains.

...TARGET REMAINS.

...TARGET REMAINS.

Combined efforts of experts in education, cognitive sciences, computer science, and various traditional disciplines are needed.

BEAUTIFUL AACHEN AS SEEN BY OLGA CAPROTTI

